

D3.2

Participatory vulnerability analysis of mobility systems

Methodological specification for pilot city implementation during WP11 demonstration activities (M21–M32).

Revision v0.2

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Abstract

This deliverable presents the methodological specification for the participatory vulnerability analysis of urban mobility systems to be conducted in AntifragiCity pilot cities during M20–M28. It establishes the complete analytical framework required to perform the vulnerability and consequence assessment described in the Description of Action; the methodology will be applied during WP11 demonstration activities (M21–M32). D3.3 [1] (M12) and D3.4 [2] (M14) will document complementary risk analysis and decision support frameworks; empirical pilot city results will be reported in WP11 outputs.

The methodology comprises five stages: (1) definition of a vulnerability conceptual framework linking susceptibility, exposure, redundancy, and adaptive capacity to the KPI framework established in D2.3 [3]; (2) scenario framing using the D2.1 disruption taxonomy [4] and D2.5 ontology [5]; (3) quantitative assessment through the D2.3 three-layer equilibrium model [3]; (4) validation through multi-source triangulation of expert consultation (n=9), a pan-European citizen survey (n=140), and Social acceptability workshops outputs from D2.2 [6] covering Bratislava, Larissa, and AHEPA University Hospital in Thessaloniki; and (5) synthesis into vulnerability profiles and risk matrices coordinated with D3.3 risk analysis [1].

The Bratislava flood scenario is used throughout as a worked example with synthetic but realistic data to illustrate each procedural step. All parameter values in these examples are illustrative and are not derived from actual pilot city data collection.

Keywords:

Urban mobility vulnerability; disruption scenarios; multi-source validation; equilibrium modelling; KPIs; equity; risk matrices

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Abbreviations

AF	Antifragility Factor
CAW	Citizens' Assembly Workshop
CSV	Comma Separated Values)
CQ	Competency Question
FMEA	Failure Modes and Effects Analysis
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LUTI	Land-Use and Transport Interaction
MCDA	Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis
OD	Origin–Destination
PCVA	Participatory Capacity and Vulnerability Assessment
PVA	Participatory Vulnerability Analysis
PT	Public Transport
RPN	Risk Priority Number
SRI	System Responsiveness Index
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities

1 Executive summary

This deliverable specifies the vulnerability analysis methodology to be applied in pilot cities, including Bratislava, AHEPA University Hospital in Thessaloniki, and Larissa. Odesa is excluded from the current implementation phase due to ongoing conflict conditions; the methodology remains applicable, and implementation may resume when conditions permit (see Section 11.1). City applications will be carried out in subsequent project phases and documented in later WP3 outputs.

The approach builds on project assets that are already available, in particular:

- the urban disruption taxonomy and event catalogue (D2.1 [4]);
- the three-layer equilibrium and KPI performance framework (D2.3 [3], operational layer only);
- the ontology, knowledge graph schema, and competency questions underpinning semantic integration across the project (D2.5 [5]);
- the land-use and urban dynamics perspective (D3.1 [7]).
- the social acceptability workshops from D2.2 [6]

This deliverable specifies a practical methodology for participatory vulnerability analysis. It does not report full pilot-city implementation results; those will be documented in later project deliverables once scenarios and inputs are validated. The methodology is structured as a five-stage workflow:

1. **Stage 1: Vulnerability conceptual framework.** Define vulnerability in terms of susceptibility, exposure, redundancy and adaptive capacity, and link these concepts to the KPIs and performance measures already formalised in D2.3 [3].
2. **Stage 2: Scenario framing.** Translate city-relevant questions into disruption scenarios by combining the D2.1 taxonomy [4] with the D2.5 ontology and competency questions [5], producing model-ready inputs.
3. **Stage 3: Quantitative vulnerability assessment.** Use the D2.3 equilibrium model [3] to compare baseline and disturbed states and compute performance-based vulnerability indicators from KPI changes.
4. **Stage 4: City consultation and validation.** Validate and refine scenarios and indicator choices through structured citizen forums and questionnaires, and elicit local knowledge on adaptive capacity.
5. **Stage 5: Synthesis and risk profiling.** Summarise results into vulnerability profiles and risk matrices, coordinating with D3.3 risk analysis [1] for likelihood/severity inputs and joint prioritisation.

Stage 4 validation integrated expert consultation, a pan-European citizen survey, and social acceptability workshops outputs from D2.2 [6] across three pilot cities. Key findings confirmed flooding and public transport disruptions as highest-priority scenarios, and travel time and accessibility as the leading citizen KPI priorities (Larissa forum, n=24). Full validation details are provided in Section 8.

2 Introduction

European cities face growing exposure to transport disruptions originating from climate change, ageing infrastructure, and socio-political instability [8, 9]. Existing planning frameworks address these risks primarily through robustness design, engineering systems to resist known loads, or through recovery planning, restoring pre-disruption states after an event [10]. Both approaches share a common limitation: they treat disruption as an aberration to be minimised rather than as information from which a system can learn and adapt. Taleb's [11, 12] concept of antifragility, the property of systems that improve under stress, provides a more demanding but more appropriate benchmark for twenty-first century urban infrastructure, and it is the organising principle of the AntifragiCity project.

AntifragiCity addresses this challenge by developing a new urban mobility governance approach that enables cities to understand their business-as-usual operations (defined as their state of equilibrium), monitor near real-time stressors and deviations from this baseline, assess potential implications through simulation capabilities, and inform adapted decision-making to mitigate consequences while continuously enhancing sustainability and resilience. The project implements antifragility through seven core objectives spanning resilience monitoring frameworks, event characterization ontologies, mobility triage decision support systems, multi-objective transportation management strategies, and participatory co-creation processes in demonstration cities (Thessaloniki, Bratislava, Larissa, Odesa; see Section 11.1 regarding Odesa's current status) [13].

This deliverable implements the methodological framework required to perform the vulnerability and consequence assessment of urban mobility systems. D3.3 [1] (M12) will document the complementary critical parameter identification and risk analysis framework; D3.4 [2] (M14) will specify the Mobility Triage DSS. Empirical application of the D3.2 methodology in pilot cities will take place during WP11 demonstration activities (M21–M32). This deliverable focuses specifically on developing the methodological foundation for assessing where, when, and why urban mobility systems are vulnerable to disruptions, thereby enabling targeted adaptation strategies and ultimately supporting the project's antifragility objectives. The methodology documented here will be applied in pilot cities during months 19–28, with results informing both short-term triage responses (WP3) and long-term antifragile traffic control strategies (WP4, WP5). *Scope note.* The Description of Action frames the vulnerability analysis around road networks. This deliverable extends the scope to encompass multi-modal urban mobility systems, including public transport, active modes, and intermodal connections, because pilot city evidence (D2.1 [4], D2.2 [6]) demonstrates that disruption consequences are shaped by modal alternatives and transfer options, not by road network topology alone. The road network remains a core component, but treating it in isolation would understate vulnerability for car-less and transit-dependent populations and would be inconsistent with the equity objectives of the project. This broader framing constitutes a methodological improvement over the original task specification.

2.1 Context and project positioning

Urban mobility systems face escalating disruption from multiple sources operating across different temporal and spatial scales. Daily stressors include traffic congestion, construction activities, and routine service interruptions. Mid-scale disruptions encompass extreme weather events (flooding, heatwaves), infrastructure failures, labor strikes, and public health emergencies. Large-scale crises involve major natural disasters, cyberattacks on critical infrastructure, and geopolitical instability [9]. These disruptions interact with long-term urban dynamics, demographic shifts, land-use changes, climate change, and technological transformations, creating complex vulnerability patterns that vary across cities, neighborhoods, and population groups [14].

Traditional transport planning has focused primarily on optimizing performance under normal conditions: minimizing travel times, maximizing network capacity, and meeting projected demand growth. Resilience considerations, when included, typically address single hazard types in isolation (e.g., flood risk assessment for specific infrastructure assets) or adopt generic robustness principles without differentiation by local context [15]. This approach has three critical limitations: (1) it underestimates the severity and frequency of compound and cascading disruptions [16], (2) it fails to capture how vulnerability manifests differently across socio-demographic groups, particularly affecting elderly, disabled, low-income, and car-less populations disproportionately [17], and (3) it provides limited practical guidance for prioritizing among competing adaptation invest-

ments when resources are constrained.

AntifragiCity responds to these limitations by developing an integrated analytical framework that treats vulnerability assessment not as a one-time technical exercise but as an ongoing process embedded within adaptive governance. WP3, within which this deliverable sits, translates this vision into operational practice through the concept of *mobility triage*, structured decision-making under uncertainty to prioritize responses when disruptions exceed routine coping capacity. Just as medical triage allocates scarce emergency resources based on severity, urgency, and treatment feasibility, mobility triage requires cities to assess which system components, corridors, and user groups face greatest vulnerability, which disruptions warrant immediate intervention versus longer-term adaptation, and how short-term responses interact with strategic resilience-building.

This deliverable addresses the foundational question underpinning triage decisions: *where and why is the urban mobility system vulnerable?* This requires moving beyond qualitative risk registers or expert opinion to develop systematic, evidence-based vulnerability profiles that combine quantitative performance modeling (leveraging D2.3's equilibrium framework and KPIs [3]) with participatory stakeholder knowledge (acknowledging that local practitioners possess critical insights about operational constraints, adaptive capacity, and community priorities not captured in models). The methodology must balance analytical rigor with practical implementability, recognizing that pilot cities have heterogeneous data availability, technical capacity, and institutional arrangements.

The vulnerability assessment developed in this deliverable serves multiple project functions. First, it provides the evidence base for risk analysis [1], enabling integration of system-level performance impacts with component-level failure probabilities. Second, it informs T3.4's Mobility Triage Decision Support System (DSS) by identifying which scenarios merit detailed agent-based modeling and which can be addressed through simpler response protocols documented in T3.5's Mobility Triage Handbook. Third, it establishes baseline conditions against which WP4's antifragile traffic control strategies and WP5's SUMA (Simulator for Urban Mobility Antifragility) will be evaluated. If interventions cannot demonstrably reduce vulnerability for priority scenarios, they fail the antifragility test. Fourth, it provides the spatial and demographic targeting criteria for WP6's living labs, ensuring that demonstration activities address genuine rather than hypothetical vulnerabilities.

Beyond its internal project role, this deliverable contributes to broader European policy objectives. The EU's Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities Mission emphasizes not only emissions reduction but also climate adaptation and resilience, recognizing that decarbonization strategies must account for increasing climate-related disruptions [18]. The Urban Mobility Framework's focus on multimodal accessibility and equity aligns directly with D3.2's emphasis on distributional vulnerability analysis [19]. The Critical Infrastructure Resilience Directive requires Member States to assess vulnerabilities in essential services including transport, with particular attention to cascading effects and interdependencies [20], precisely the cross-sectoral perspective embedded in AntifragiCity's approach.

Methodologically, this deliverable is designed as a *procedural specification* rather than a results report. The focus is on describing *how* vulnerability analysis will be conducted systematically across different city contexts, with what inputs, following which steps, and producing what standardized outputs. D3.3 [1] (M12) and D3.4 [2] (M14) document complementary WP3 frameworks. Quantitative application of the vulnerability methodology (Stage 3 model implementation) will take place during WP11 demonstration activities (M21–M32), with data collection and model runs coordinated through the demonstration work package. Stage 4 has provided preliminary validation of scenario relevance and stakeholder priorities; full parameter validation will occur during pilot city demonstration activities (M21–M32).

This sequencing reflects a deliberate choice: publishing methods before results allows peer review of analytical approach independently of empirical findings, supports transparency and reproducibility, and enables other cities to apply the framework before AntifragiCity's demonstration phase concludes.

The methodology integrates four preceding AntifragiCity deliverables, each contributing essential building blocks: D2.1 (Urban Event Mapping [4]) provides the disruption taxonomy and evidence base for scenario definitions; D2.3 [3] (Establishing Urban States of Equilibrium) supplies the quantitative performance model linking network conditions to system-level KPIs; D2.5 (Ontology of Urban Events Development [5]) provides the semantic backbone and knowledge graph schema underpinning integration across the project, including competency questions used in scenario framing; and D3.1 (Analysis of Transport Network and Land-Use Dynamics [7]) characterizes the urban context within which transport vulnerability manifests. Rather than duplicating content from these deliverables, this deliverable specifies precisely how their outputs are synthesized into a coherent vulnerability assessment workflow. This integration itself represents a methodological contribution: existing

literature typically treats event catalogs, performance indicators, and spatial analysis as separate domains, whereas D3.2 demonstrates their operational linkage.

2.2 Relation to previous AntifragiCity deliverables

The vulnerability methodology builds upon and synthesizes outputs from four previous deliverables, each addressing a distinct analytical need. Understanding these dependencies is essential for interpreting the methodology's scope and recognizing how it fits within the project's overall technical architecture.

D2.1 Urban Event Mapping [4] established the project's disruption taxonomy and evidence base. Through systematic review of academic literature, disaster databases (EM-DAT, and stakeholder surveys across pilot cities, D2.1 [4] developed a two-dimensional classification of urban mobility disruptions: by *domain* (environmental/weather, technological/cyber, socio-political, infrastructure/physical, public health) and by *scale* (daily stressors, mid-scale disruptions, large-scale crises) [11, 9]. Each taxonomy cell contains documented event instances with severity ratings, return period estimates, and observed impact descriptions. This deliverable uses this taxonomy in Stage 2 (scenario framing) to ensure that pilot-city scenarios are (a) grounded in empirical precedent rather than speculation, (b) comparable across cities through common classification, and (c) calibrated for severity using evidence-based multipliers. The D2.1 event catalog [4] also provides the initial likelihood estimates that Stage 4 validation will validate or adjust based on local historical experience.

D2.3 [3] Establishing Urban States of Equilibrium implemented the project's core theoretical concept: that antifragility requires first defining what "normal" system performance looks like (the equilibrium state) before perturbations can be meaningfully characterized [21]. D2.3 [3] developed a mathematical framework combining three modeling layers, traffic assignment (Wardrop user equilibrium), modal split (logit discrete choice), and system responsiveness (aggregate KPI calculation), embedded within a dual-model architecture comprising a Target-Setting Model (which quantifies post-shock performance targets through the Antifragility Factor (AF) and the Three-Layer Equilibrium Model described above. This deliverable draws exclusively on the Three-Layer Equilibrium Model for quantitative assessment; the Target-Setting Model and AF framework are not used here and are deferred to future antifragility measurement activities in WP5. This deliverable treats D2.3's equilibrium model [3] as a quantitative engine: Stage 3 (quantitative vulnerability assessment) runs the model twice for each scenario, once under baseline conditions, once under disrupted conditions, and calculates vulnerability as the percentage performance loss $\Delta E_s = 1 - (E_s^{\text{post}}/E^{\text{base}})$. Critically, this deliverable does not introduce new performance metrics or modify D2.3's formulations [3]; it specifies how to systematically apply the existing framework to vulnerability questions.

D2.5 Ontology of Urban Events Development [5] provides the semantic backbone of the AntifragiCity knowledge infrastructure. Its architecture is organised around a 12-class domain-independent meta-model: `TransportElement`, `MobilityService`, `DisruptionEvent`, `SystemState`, `Scenario`, `EnvironmentFactor`, `Actor`, `GovernanceInstrument`, `SpatialUnit`, `TemporalUnit`, `Observation`, and `ResponseAction`. These classes are further specialised into domain-specific subclasses (e.g., `EquityGroup` as a subclass of `Actor`; `NaturalHazard`, `CyberAttack` as subclasses of `DisruptionEvent`). This deliverable draws on this architecture in Stage 2 scenario framing to map city stakeholder questions onto structured model parameters: `SpatialUnit` instances correspond to traffic analysis zones or network links; `Actor/EquityGroup` subclass instances partition the OD matrix by demographic attributes; `DisruptionEvent` severity maps to D2.3's disturbance indicator [3] $D_{\text{eff}}(t)$. D3.2's Stage 2 scenario framing procedure systematically exploits these ontology mappings, using competency questions (CQs) as the interface between city stakeholders' natural language descriptions and the modeler's technical parameter specifications. This approach addresses a recognized challenge in participatory modeling: ensuring that stakeholder input is genuinely incorporated rather than cosmetically acknowledged [22].

D3.1 Analysis of Transport Network and Land-Use Dynamics [7] established the theoretical and conceptual foundations for understanding how land use and transport networks interact under disruption. Drawing on LUTI theory [23, 24] and a review of urban mobility models (15-minute city, Transit-Oriented Development, sociotechnical systems), D3.1 [7] developed a holistic conceptual framework (Figure 13 of D3.1 [7]) linking exogenous disruption drivers to exposure, sensitivity, vulnerability, accessibility impacts, resilience responses, and antifragility within the transport-land-use system. This deliverable draws on this framework in three ways: (1) D3.1's hazard-exposure-vulnerability structure [7] (components D, E, S, V, TI, TN in Figure 13 of D3.1 [7]) informs Stage 1's operational definitions of susceptibility, exposure, and redundancy; (2) D3.1's characterisation [7] of how urban form and land-use mix shape accessibility and redundancy guides scenario framing in Stage 2; and

(3) D3.1’s resilience–antifragility framework [7] contextualises the vulnerability profiles produced in Stage 5. D3.1 [7] is a theoretical and conceptual deliverable; it does not provide city-specific spatial data. All spatial inputs required for pilot city implementation (population distributions, critical facility locations, land-use layers) are sourced directly from municipal GIS systems and national statistics, as specified in Annex D.

Beyond these four primary dependencies, this deliverable also interfaces with D2.2 social acceptability workshops [6] integration, also with D2.7’s KPI Framework Development [25] (which informed D2.3’s indicator selection [3]) and will coordinate closely with D3.3’s risk and failure mode analysis [1] through the integration protocol specified in Annex E. The methodology’s value lies partly in demonstrating how these diverse analytical components, event taxonomies, performance models, semantic ontologies, spatial analysis, can be operationally synthesized rather than remaining conceptually disconnected as often occurs in urban resilience research [26].

2.3 Vulnerability, risk and antifragility: conceptual distinctions

Three related concepts are used throughout this deliverable and must be defined precisely, as the transport resilience literature uses them inconsistently [26, 10]. The definitions below establish the terminological conventions that govern all subsequent sections; where upstream deliverables use different phrasing, the mapping to these conventions is noted explicitly.

Vulnerability describes the propensity of a system to experience performance loss when exposed to a disruptive event. Following the UNDP Climate Change Adaptation framework and consistent with IPCC usage, vulnerability is understood here as a function of *exposure* (the degree to which elements and users fall within a hazard footprint), *sensitivity* (the degree to which the system is affected by the hazard, termed *susceptibility* in the operational formulas of Stage 1 to distinguish it from hazard severity), and *lack of adaptive capacity* (the absence of institutional and operational ability to anticipate, absorb, and learn from disruption) [27, 28]. In this deliverable, vulnerability is quantified through KPI-based performance loss (ΔE_s) rather than treated as a qualitative property.

Risk combines vulnerability with the *likelihood* of a hazard occurring and the *severity* of its consequences. In the risk matrices of Stage 5, *impact* refers to the combined effect of vulnerability and severity: a scenario’s impact class is determined by ΔE_s (performance-based vulnerability) and, where available, D3.3 severity scores [1], with an equity adjustment applied post-hoc. Likelihood is estimated through frequency-based evidence triangulated across sources (Annex C).

Antifragility describes a system’s capacity not merely to resist or recover from disturbance but to improve its configuration or governance as a consequence of stress [11]. This concept goes beyond resilience (return to baseline) by requiring that repeated exposure to disruption yields measurable performance gains over successive cycles. Antifragility measurement is outside the scope of this deliverable; it will be addressed through D2.3’s Antifragility Factor and Target-Setting Model [3] in WP5 activities.

These distinctions have direct operational implications. *Terminological note.* Throughout this deliverable, *susceptibility* is used in the operational formulas (Stage 1, Equation 8) as the implementation of the concept that IPCC and UNDP frameworks term *sensitivity*. The term *sensitivity* is reserved for its statistical meaning (sensitivity analysis of parameter choices). *Impact*, as used in the Stage 5 risk matrices, denotes the combined consequence of vulnerability and severity for a given scenario; it is not synonymous with vulnerability alone. *Severity* refers to the intrinsic magnitude of harm caused by a hazard event, as distinct from the system’s propensity to be affected (vulnerability). These conventions apply throughout Sections 5–9 and the annexes. Vulnerability assessment identifies susceptible elements and exposure patterns but does not estimate disruption probabilities, that requires risk analysis integrating D3.2’s impact evidence with likelihood data from D2.1 [4] and D3.3 [1]. Antifragility measurement (future WP5 activities) will compare not just baseline versus disturbed performance but also performance trajectory over repeated disruption cycles, does the system’s response improve with experience, indicating learning and adaptation [11], this deliverable establishes the prerequisite baseline: reliable vulnerability profiles are necessary before risk prioritization or antifragility enhancement can proceed systematically.

The document is organised as follows. Section 3 reviews the literature on urban mobility vulnerability and identifies four methodological gaps. Section 4 formulates the research questions and explains how the five-stage methodology addresses the identified gaps. Sections 5 through 9 present each stage of the methodology in full, including worked examples using synthetic Bratislava data. Section 10 discusses integration with land-use dynamics drawing on the D3.1 conceptual framework [7]. Section 11 examines pilot city applications, methodological contributions, limitations, and implementation guidance. Section 12 revisits the research questions, articulates limitations and follow-on actions, and sets out next steps and future research directions. Annexes A–E provide operational materials.

3 Literature review

This section is intentionally focused rather than comprehensive: it highlights key conceptual frameworks, methodological approaches, and evidence gaps that inform the design choices made in later sections.

3.1 Urban mobility vulnerability concepts

Work on transport vulnerability commonly focuses on how disruptions reduce system performance, which parts of the network are critical, and how impacts propagate to users and locations [9, 29]. In this literature, vulnerability is often linked to (i) exposure of assets and users, (ii) susceptibility of elements to a given hazard, and (iii) the availability of alternatives and recovery options.

Resilience discussions also emphasise a small number of recurring properties. A commonly cited framing highlights robustness and rapidity as outcome-oriented properties, supported by redundancy and resourcefulness as enabling properties [10]. In this deliverable we use similar language, but we keep the focus on practical templates and measurable indicators.

Accessibility is frequently used as a bridge between transport performance and social outcomes. Reviews note that accessibility measures differ in their interpretation and data needs, but they are useful for linking transport changes to land-use patterns and opportunity reachability [14]. This is relevant for AntifragiCity because equity reporting requires more than network-level metrics.

Equity and justice perspectives stress that the same disruption can have very different consequences across groups. Reviews emphasise the need to connect transport impacts to distributive questions and to use accessibility-based evidence when discussing fairness [30]. Related work on social exclusion highlights that transport disadvantage is context dependent and may not be visible if analysis only reports averages [17].

3.2 Existing methodological approaches

Many studies represent transport as a graph and use criticality or importance measures to identify links or nodes whose loss causes large system effects [29]. These methods are clear and communicable, but they can under-represent behavioural adaptation and distributional impacts unless combined with demand and user-group information.

Flow- and OD-based approaches quantify disruption impacts through changes in travel times, modal costs, and accessibility [14]. Their principal limitation is sensitivity to OD matrix quality: in many European cities, household travel surveys are conducted infrequently (often decennially), meaning baseline demand data may not reflect current conditions, let alone post-disruption behaviour. AntifragiCity addresses this through the tiered implementation framework (Section 7), which explicitly acknowledges data constraints and calibrates analytical depth accordingly.

Multi-criteria approaches allow KPIs with incommensurable units to be aggregated into composite indices. The critical weakness identified by [26] is that weight selection is often opaque: analysts choose weights that reflect their own priorities rather than those of affected communities, and sensitivity to weight choice is rarely tested. This deliverable attempts to address this through the Stage 4 citizen consultation protocol, though as Section 11 acknowledges, the validation coverage achieved is partial and city-specific.

Participatory vulnerability assessment. A distinct strand of vulnerability analysis emphasises community-based and participatory methods, in which affected populations contribute directly to identifying hazards, assessing exposure, and prioritising responses. Participatory Vulnerability Analysis (PVA) and Participatory Capacity and Vulnerability Assessment (PCVA) frameworks developed in the disaster risk reduction community [31, 32] treat local knowledge not as supplementary but as primary evidence, using tools such as community

mapping, seasonal calendars, and deliberative ranking exercises. These approaches are strong on context sensitivity and equity visibility but are typically qualitative and difficult to integrate with network-level performance models. In AntifragiCity, Stage 4 adopts the core PVA principle that vulnerability identification must include the perspectives of those affected, while embedding citizen and expert inputs within a quantitative framework that links participatory evidence to measurable KPI changes. Risk frameworks such as FMEA provide structured ways to organise failure modes, severity, and prioritisation [33]. However, they do not automatically provide a system-level performance link. In AntifragiCity, vulnerability evidence from this deliverable is designed to connect scenario performance changes to the prioritisation work in D3.3 [1].

Table 1 summarises this comparison at a high level.

Table 1: Comparison of vulnerability assessment approaches (high-level).

Approach	Typical strengths	Common limitations	AntifragiCity use
Network-based	Clear identification of critical elements	Often weak on behaviour and equity detail	Used for screening and mapping, complemented by D2.3 KPIs [3]
Flow/OD-based	Captures demand and accessibility changes	Depends on OD inputs and modelling assumptions	Implemented through D2.3 baseline [3] vs. disturbed equilibria
MCDA	Combines multiple KPIs transparently	Weight choice can be subjective	Weights elicited via Stage 4 protocol
FMEA/Risk	Structured failure-mode documentation	Weak link to system performance by itself	Linked via this deliverable scenario evidence and D3.3 [1] integration
Participatory (PVA/PCVA)	Strong on local context, equity visibility, community ownership	Typically qualitative; difficult to link to system-level performance metrics	Stage 4 protocol integrates participatory evidence with quantitative KPI framework

3.3 Land use-transport vulnerability integration

Land use and transport are linked through accessibility. Where people live and where activities are located shape travel demand, while changes in transport performance can influence longer-term location patterns. For vulnerability analysis, this matters because disruptions do not only affect network performance: they also affect access to land-use functions such as healthcare, education and employment linked through accessibility [14].

Most land-use-transport interaction (LUTI) models study these feedbacks over longer time horizons. In AntifragiCity, this deliverable does not introduce a new LUTI model. Instead, we use land-use information in a practical way to (i) frame scenarios around essential functions, (ii) define exposure and equity groups, and (iii) interpret vulnerability profiles in relation to land-use patterns, consistent with the conceptual framework developed in D3.1 [7, 23, 24]

3.4 State of the art: antifragility, learning, and semantics-enabled vulnerability analysis

A practical limitation in much transport vulnerability work is that it implements *resilience* mainly as maintaining or rapidly recovering performance after a disruption, while giving less methodological attention to how cities can *learn from shocks* and improve future response capabilities. This distinction is central to AntifragiCity’s “progress beyond state-of-the-art” positioning: rather than focusing only on “bounce-back” outcomes, the project targets an *antifragile* orientation in which variability and stress can lead to improved configurations and governance responses [11]. For this deliverable, this matters because scenario/KPI design should not only represent immediate performance loss (e.g., delay, accessibility reduction), but also record the conditions under

which adaptive capacity, redundancy, and operational learning reduce *future* vulnerability (linking directly to the equilibrium framing and the procedural stages in later sections).

Relatedly, vulnerability assessment practice often separates (i) technical system metrics (network criticality, delay, capacity loss) from (ii) participatory or consensus-based prioritisation (citizen or expert weights), treating the latter as an add-on rather than a structured component of the analytical workflow. A relevant strand of resilience assessment combines structured elicitation (e.g., Delphi) with multi-criteria aggregation (e.g., AHP) to make prioritisation transparent and repeatable. This deliverable aligns with this “structured consensus” logic by formalising where stakeholder inputs enter the workflow (e.g., scenario relevance, severity calibration, and KPI emphasis), while retaining traceability to the quantitative disturbance/equilibrium comparisons produced by the modelling chain.

A second “quick win” alignment from the proposal concerns *interoperability and semantics*. Vulnerability analysis in practice is increasingly multi-source (administrative logs, sensor feeds, operator reports, stakeholder narratives). Without a shared semantic layer, however, the same disruption can be classified differently across cities and work packages, undermining reproducibility and comparability. This is especially important for this deliverable because (i) event typing determines the scenario catalogue, (ii) exposure definitions determine which assets and populations are considered at risk, and (iii) KPI computation requires consistent mapping from events to affected network components and service functions. In that sense, this deliverable does not treat “ontology/semantics” as a purely technical infrastructure topic; it treats semantic coherence as a precondition for credible vulnerability evidence that can be transferred across pilots and reused in later prioritisation (D3.3) and intervention design.

Finally, the proposal’s arguments concerning *digital-twin-enabled decision support* motivate why this deliverable emphasises a tiered implementation logic (data readiness, modelling depth, and interpretability). Digital twin approaches for transport/road infrastructure highlight the value of integrating heterogeneous data streams with decision workflows and governance requirements, but they also make clear that real-world deployment is constrained by data availability, latency, and operational complexity [34]. This deliverable, therefore, frames vulnerability assessment as a staged, auditable process: this deliverable’s aim is not simply to identify “critical links”, but to produce scenario evidence that is sufficiently structured (and semantically coherent) to support downstream triage and prioritisation across cities under realistic evidence constraints.

3.5 Summary of addressed gaps

Four methodological gaps emerge from this review and directly motivate the design choices in this deliverable.

Existing vulnerability assessments often fail to effectively implement the connection between disruption catalogues, performance models, and semantic ontologies within a single reproducible workflow. This deliverable addresses this by specifying how D2.1 [4], D2.3 [3], and D2.5 [5] outputs are synthesised at each procedural stage, reducing the interpretive discretion left to implementing analysts.

Second, distributional impacts remain under-reported in transport vulnerability literature [17, 30]. Aggregate metrics such as total vehicle-hours lost conceal disproportionate burdens on elderly, low-income, and car-less populations. This deliverable incorporates equity-disaggregated KPI reporting as a methodological requirement rather than an optional supplement.

Third, there is a persistent gap between resilience concepts and practical assessment procedures [26]. The translation from theoretical constructs (redundancy, adaptive capacity) to measurable indicators and model inputs is rarely made explicit. This deliverable provides this translation through the component-to-KPI mapping in Stage 1 and the scenario parameterisation protocol in Stage 2.

Fourth, the literature on urban transport vulnerability has been dominated by technical and engineering perspectives, with limited integration of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) methods [17, 30]. Quantitative models routinely omit the lived experience and contextual knowledge held by citizens and local practitioners, whose understanding of adaptive capacity, equity priorities, and acceptable risk thresholds cannot be derived from network data alone [22]. The word “Participatory” in this task’s title is not incidental: it reflects a deliberate commitment to embedding SSH instruments, citizen surveys, deliberative assemblies, and expert consultation, within a quantitative methodology, rather than treating them as optional supplementary commentary. This deliverable addresses this gap through the Stage 4 protocol, which integrates social acceptability workshop ev-

idence from D2.2 [6] alongside quantitative KPI outputs, and through the scenario framing process (Stage 2), which begins from citizen-articulated competency questions rather than analyst-defined scenarios.

4 Methodology

Four methodological gaps identified in the literature review (Section 3) directly shape the structure of the methodology proposed here. The first gap, the absence of an integrated workflow linking event catalogues, performance models, and semantic ontologies within a single reproducible procedure [G1], motivates the sequential five-stage design, in which each stage has explicitly defined inputs drawn from prior published work [9, 21] and outputs consumed by the next. The second gap, the systematic under-reporting of distributional impacts on vulnerable populations [G2] [17, 30], motivates the mandatory disaggregation of performance loss by user group embedded in Stages 1 and 3, and the equity adjustment rule in Stage 5. The third gap, the persistent failure to translate resilience concepts into practical, measurable assessment procedures [G3] [26], motivates the explicit component-to-KPI mapping in Stage 1 and the parameterisation protocol in Stage 2, both of which reduce the interpretive discretion that has historically made vulnerability assessments difficult to replicate or compare across cities. The fourth, limited integration of SSH methods [17] will be covered in Stage 4 and Stage 5.

The five stages address these gaps in sequence:

1. **Stage 1 (Section 5):** Vulnerability conceptual framework [addresses G1, G3], defining susceptibility, exposure, redundancy, and adaptive capacity, and mapping each to measurable indicators from an established performance framework [21].
2. **Stage 2 (Section 6):** Scenario framing [addresses G1], translating stakeholder questions into model-ready disruption scenarios using a published disruption taxonomy and knowledge ontology.
3. **Stage 3 (Section 7):** Quantitative assessment [addresses G1, G2], applying the equilibrium model to compute performance changes and disaggregated vulnerability scores by user group.
4. **Stage 4 (Section 8):** Stakeholder consultation and validation [addresses G2, G3, G4], embedding SSH knowledge through citizen surveys, social acceptability workshops, and expert Delphi to validate, weight, and contextualise quantitative outputs.
5. **Stage 5 (Section 9):** Synthesis and risk profiling [addresses G1, G2, G3, G4], combining quantitative and participatory inputs into vulnerability profiles and risk matrices.

Note on data status: numerical values in the worked examples in Stages 2, 3, and 5 are synthetic. They have been constructed to be internally consistent and broadly realistic for a Central European tram network but are not derived from actual Bratislava data collection. They do not represent the findings of this deliverable and should not be cited as such. Empirical values will be established during WP11 demonstration activities (M21–M32) and reported in the corresponding WP11 outputs.

4.1 Research questions

The task leading to this deliverable pursues three interconnected objectives: to examine how vulnerability of urban mobility networks is defined and implemented in the literature; to identify the risk factors with which vulnerability is correlated and how their severity can be assessed; and to evaluate the consequences of disruptions for users and society, with explicit attention to distributional impacts across socio-demographic groups. These objectives are translated into four discrete research questions that give this deliverable its academic standing and structure the methodology in Section 4:

- RQ1** How should vulnerability of urban mobility systems be defined and implemented so that it is measurable across cities with heterogeneous data environments?
- RQ2** With which risk factors, hazard exposure, network susceptibility, redundancy, and adaptive capacity, is vulnerability correlated, and how can these factors be systematically mapped to performance indicators?
- RQ3** How can the severity of disruption consequences be assessed quantitatively for the system as a whole and for specific user and equity groups?

RQ4 How can participatory stakeholder knowledge, from expert consultation, citizen surveys, and social acceptability workshops, be rigorously integrated into a reproducible vulnerability assessment workflow?

These research questions are distinct from the D2.5 competency questions (CQs) used in Stage 2 scenario framing [5]. The RQs define the academic scope of this deliverable; the CQs are city-specific operational queries (e.g., “Which corridors become inaccessible to elderly during a flood?”) that translate stakeholder concerns into model-ready scenario parameters.

RQ1 is addressed in Stage 1 (Section 5); RQ2 in Stages 1 and 2; RQ3 in Stage 3 (Section 7); and RQ4 in Stage 4 (Section 8) and the participatory framing throughout.

5 Stage 1: Vulnerability conceptual framework

Stage 1 defines the operational meaning of vulnerability within the AntifragiCity framework, linking four conceptual components, susceptibility, exposure, redundancy, and adaptive capacity, to measurable performance indicators. This grounding is necessary because the same words are used inconsistently across the resilience literature [26, 10], and inconsistent definitions produce incomparable results across cities or studies.

Vulnerability in the present framework is understood as the potential for a transport system to lose performance under a given disruptive event. It is not an inherent property of the network alone, but a relational concept that emerges from the interaction between the characteristics of the system, the nature of the hazard, and the options available for response. Four components capture this interaction.

Susceptibility refers to the inherent fragility of network elements to a particular type of disturbance. An element is more susceptible if it is old, poorly maintained, or designed to standards that do not account for the hazard in question. Susceptibility is a pre-existing property of the system, independent of whether any event actually occurs.

Exposure describes the degree to which elements and users are located within the area affected by a hazard. A tram corridor running alongside a floodplain is more exposed to river flooding than one running through an elevated district, even if both corridors are equally well maintained. Exposure captures the spatial and demographic coincidence between the hazard footprint and the people or assets at risk.

Redundancy reflects the availability of alternatives: parallel routes, substitute modes, or nearby services that allow trips to be completed even when a primary element fails. A city with a dense multimodal network is inherently more redundant than one dependent on a single corridor or mode. Redundancy reduces vulnerability because it limits the performance consequences of any individual failure.

Adaptive capacity captures the ability of the system, both its institutions and its users, to anticipate, respond to, and learn from disruption. A city that can rapidly reroute services, communicate alternatives, and update plans based on experience will recover more quickly and suffer fewer long-term performance losses than one with rigid operational procedures and limited information systems.

These four components interact multiplicatively rather than additively: an element with very high redundancy may remain low-vulnerability even if susceptibility and exposure are both elevated, whereas an element with no alternatives amplifies the consequences of any capacity loss. The operational formulas that implement this structure are introduced below, following a summary of the performance indicators to which each component is mapped.

The equilibrium performance framework [3] defines twelve Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) aggregated into a composite performance index E . For vulnerability analysis, these indicators are used directly, classified below by their role in assessing system performance loss under disruption.

1. **Mobility throughput** $M(t)$: Average multi-modal trips per capita per hour (trips/h-cap)
2. **Redundancy ratio** $R(t)$: Ratio of dormant links to active links, indicating network alternatives (dimensionless)
3. **Adaptation velocity** $A(t)$: Rate of change of modal-share diversity over time (%/day)
4. **Network information entropy** $C(t)$: Shannon entropy of OD flow distribution, normalized to current topology (dimensionless [0,1])
5. **Effective disturbance** $D_{\text{eff}}(t)$: Domain/recency/source-weighted disruption magnitude from D2.1 [4] (dimensionless [0,1])
6. **Stress index** $S(t)$: Sum of (volume/capacity) \times speed_drop across network (dimensionless [0,1])
7. **Equity penalty** $Q(t)$: Stratified inequality measure of accessibility minutes (dimensionless [0,1]); implemented as either the Theil-T entropy index or the Gini coefficient, applied consistently throughout a given city assessment.
8. **Pricing/participation index** $P(t)$: Composite index from time-varying fares, weighted by ridership (index [0,1])

9. **Behavioral compliance** $B(t)$: Weighted average of route guidance compliance, mode shift willingness, temporal flexibility (index [0,1])
10. **Energy resilience** $E_{\text{energy}}(t)$: EV-grid resilience score from SCADA data (dimensionless [0,1])
11. **ICT uptime** $E_{\text{ICT}}(t)$: Telecom network uptime percentage during event (% as [0,1])
12. **Intermodal synergy** $I(t)$: Normalized sum of inverse transfer distances between transport modes (dimensionless [0,1])

In addition to the twelve D2.3 KPIs listed above, this deliverable introduces a thirteenth indicator for vulnerability analysis:

Land-use accessibility pressure $\Lambda(t)$ [D3.2 extension]: Weighted mismatch between the spatial distribution of essential service destinations (healthcare, employment, education) and the population groups dependent on the transport network to reach them, normalised by baseline accessibility levels (dimensionless [0,1]). Higher values indicate greater functional exposure: large numbers of car-less or mobility-impaired residents located far from critical facilities in zones where transport alternatives are limited. This indicator is sourced from municipal GIS and census data per Annex D rather than from D2.3 [3], which does not include land-use accessibility as a KPI. It extends the D2.3 framework for the specific purpose of vulnerability analysis and is not part of the composite performance index \bar{E} defined in D2.3 [3].

Formula for $\Lambda(t)$:

$$\Lambda(t) = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{G}|} \sum_{g \in \mathcal{G}} \frac{A_g^{\text{base}} - A_g(t)}{A_g^{\text{base}}} \cdot \phi_g \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{G} is the set of equity groups (elderly, low-income, car-less), $A_g(t)$ is the Hansen-style accessibility measure for group g at time t (defined in Annex B, Indicator P3), A_g^{base} is baseline accessibility, and $\phi_g \in [0, 1]$ is a group vulnerability weight elicited through Stage 4 consultation (default: equal weights). $\Lambda = 0$ indicates no change in land-use accessibility pressure; $\Lambda = 1$ indicates complete loss of access to essential services for the most vulnerable group. *Distinction from existing KPIs.* $\Lambda(t)$ captures a dimension not represented in the D2.3 indicator set [3]. The equity penalty $Q(t)$ measures inequality in transport-level accessibility *within* the network (distributional spread of travel times or generalised costs across groups). $\Lambda(t)$ measures the *functional* mismatch between where vulnerable populations are located and where essential services exist, weighted by transport dependency. A city could score well on Q (equitable travel times) yet poorly on Λ if car-less elderly residents are concentrated far from hospitals in zones with limited transit. To prevent double-counting, Λ is computed from GIS and census inputs independently of the equilibrium model outputs and enters the vulnerability workflow as an exposure modifier only; it is excluded from the composite performance index \bar{E} and from E_{vuln} .

Not all twelve indicators are equally relevant for vulnerability assessment. Table 2 classifies them by the role each plays, distinguishing those that directly measure performance loss from those that capture adaptive or contextual factors, and noting which should be treated as scenario inputs rather than outputs.

Rationale for exclusions:

- D_{eff} is the *input* disturbance that defines the scenario (Stage 2), not an *output* measuring system response. Vulnerability is measured by how other KPIs change given D_{eff} .
- $P(t)$ and $B(t)$ depend on policy responses and user behavior that are difficult to predict ex-ante; they are more relevant for evaluating adaptation strategies (WP4) than baseline vulnerability.
- E_{energy} and E_{ICT} require real-time infrastructure data (SCADA, telecom logs) not available in most pilot cities at Tier 2.

In addition to the KPI set, D2.3 [3] uses an event disturbance indicator $D_{\text{eff}}(t)$ to represent the intensity of the disruption over time. In practice, this provides a consistent way to connect scenario definitions (domain, severity, evidence) to the model shock profile.

The twelve indicators are combined into a composite performance index \bar{E} , following the weighting structure established in the equilibrium framework [3]. For vulnerability analysis, however, a simplified form is used that excludes the scenario input indicator D_{eff} and the harder-to-measure behavioural indicators, as explained below. The performance index combines positive and negative components:

$$\bar{E}(t) = \lambda \bar{E}^+(t) - (1 - \lambda) \bar{E}^-(t), \quad \lambda = 0.70 \text{ (default)} \quad (2)$$

Table 2: D2.3 KPI classification [3] for vulnerability analysis.

Category	KPIs	Vulnerability role
Core vulnerability (always included)	M, R, C, S, Q, I	Direct measures of performance loss, system alternatives, stress, and equity impacts under disruption
Extended (include when data available)	$A, E_{\text{energy}}, E_{\text{ICT}}$	Capture adaptive capacity and infrastructure dependencies; require specialized data sources
Context-dependent (optional)	P, B	Pricing and behavioral responses are relevant for specific scenarios but harder to measure and predict
Scenario input (not an output KPI)	D_{eff}	Defines disruption magnitude; used as scenario parameter in Stage 2, not as vulnerability outcome
Land-use extension (D3.2 only)	Λ	Captures functional exposure from land-use-transport mismatch; sourced from GIS/census data; not part of D2.3 \bar{E} composite

where:

$$\bar{E}^+(t) = \alpha_1 M + \alpha_2 R + \alpha_3 A + \alpha_4 C + \omega_1 E_{\text{energy}} + \omega_2 E_{\text{ICT}} + \zeta I + \pi P + \mu B \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{E}^-(t) = \beta_1 D_{\text{eff}} + \beta_2 S + \theta Q \quad (4)$$

For vulnerability analysis, we simplify by excluding scenario input (D_{eff}) and difficult-to-measure indicators (P, B):

Vulnerability-focused performance index (9 KPIs):

$$E_{\text{vuln}}(t) = \frac{w_M M + w_R R + w_A A + w_C C + w_I I + w_E (E_{\text{energy}} + E_{\text{ICT}})/2 - w_S S - w_Q Q}{\sum w_k} \quad (5)$$

with default equal weights $w_k = 1$ for included KPIs, normalized to $[0,1]$.

Relationship to D2.3 performance index [3]. The D2.3 composite index \bar{E} measures equilibrium performance under given conditions. The vulnerability-focused index E_{vuln} defined in Equation 5 measures *performance loss sensitivity*: it is designed specifically to quantify relative change between baseline and disturbed states, not to characterise absolute performance levels. E_{vuln} is *not* a simplified version of \bar{E} . It is a separate construct defined for the specific purpose of measuring relative performance change under disruption. The two indices share KPI inputs but use different weighting structures, include different indicator subsets, and apply different normalisation conventions. Analysts must not mix results from \bar{E} and E_{vuln} in the same comparison. ΔE_s as defined in the equation below is always computed using the same index formulation for both baseline and post-event states.

Specifically, the Tier 2 index:

$$E_{\text{Tier2}} = \frac{M + R + C + I - S - Q + 2}{6} \quad (6)$$

uses a fixed offset of +2 to ensure the range $[0, 1]$ given the six-KPI subset. This offset has no theoretical relationship to D2.3's $\lambda = 0.70$ weighting parameter [3] and should not be interpreted as such. It is a pragmatic normalisation specific to this deliverable.

Tier 2 simplified index (6 core KPIs):

For cities with standard data availability, the Tier 2 index uses only core vulnerability KPIs:

$$E_{\text{Tier2}}(t) = \frac{M + R + C + I - S - Q + 2}{6} \quad (7)$$

The +2 offset is a pragmatic correction: with $S, Q \in [0, 1]$ both subtracted, the numerator minimum is $0 + 0 + 0 + 0 - 1 - 1 + 2 = 0$ and maximum is $1 + 1 + 1 + 1 - 0 - 0 + 2 = 6$, giving $E_{\text{Tier2}} \in [0, 1]$. This offset is specific to the 6-KPI subset and is *not* derived from D2.3's λ -based normalization [3]; the two formulations are not directly comparable.

Normalisation convention. All KPIs entering E_{vuln} and E_{Tier2} are normalised to $[0, 1]$ using theoretical bounds: each indicator is defined on $[0, 1]$ by construction (see Annex B for individual formulas). This avoids the need for min-max scaling, which would make results dependent on the sample of scenarios evaluated and would undermine cross-city comparability. Where raw data require transformation to $[0, 1]$ (e.g., stress index S capped at $v/c = 1.2$), the capping rule is documented in Annex B. All pilot cities must use the same normalisation conventions; deviations must be documented and justified in the scenario log.

In the Tier 2 formulation, all six KPIs carry equal weight. This is a deliberate default reflecting the absence of validated city-specific KPI priorities; sensitivity analysis testing alternative weight distributions is mandatory (Section 7).

Table 3 maps vulnerability components to specific KPIs.

Table 3: Vulnerability component mapping to D2.3 KPIs [3]: conceptual meaning, operational proxy, measurement logic, and known limitations.

Component	Conceptual meaning	KPI proxy	Measurement logic	Limitations / assumptions
Susceptibility	Inherent fragility of network elements to a given hazard type	$S(t)$	$\text{Sus}_i = S_i$ (normalised stress index)	Treats current stress as a proxy for structural fragility; does not capture asset age or maintenance state directly (see Annex B, Indicator S1 for richer formulation)
Exposure	Spatial and demographic overlap between hazard footprint and users/assets	$M(t), Q(t)$	$\text{Exp}_{i,s} = (\text{flow}_{i,s} / \text{max_flow}) \times D_{\text{eff},s}$	Assumes flow volume is proportional to population exposure; does not capture time-of-day variation without Tier 3 data
Redundancy	Availability of alternative routes, modes, or nearby services	$R(t), C(t), I(t)$	$\text{Red}_i = (R_i + C_i + I_i) / 3$	Equal weighting of path, entropy, and intermodal components is a default; correlated failures across alternatives are not modelled
Adaptive capacity	Ability of institutions and users to anticipate, respond to, and learn from disruption	$A(t), E_{\text{energy}}(t), E_{\text{ICT}}(t)$	$\text{Cap}_i = A_i$ (or average if infrastructure KPIs available)	Relies on adaptation velocity as proxy; institutional learning and governance readiness are not yet empirically captured (Stage 4 elicitation pending)
Functional exposure	Mismatch between vulnerable population locations and essential service access	$\Lambda(t)$ [D3.2 extension]	Equity-weighted accessibility loss from GIS/census data (Eq. 1)	One-directional land-use input; does not model feedback from disruption to location behaviour

With the KPI components defined, it is now possible to express element-level vulnerability as a single formula that brings susceptibility, exposure, redundancy, and adaptive capacity together. For network element i under scenario s , vulnerability is given by:

$$v_{i,s} = \alpha_s \cdot \text{Sus}_i \cdot \text{Exp}_{i,s} \cdot (1 - \text{Red}_i) \cdot (1 - \text{Cap}_i) \quad (8)$$

where:

- $Sus_i \in [0, 1]$: Calculated as S_i (stress index, normalized)
- $Cap_i \in [0, 1]$: $(A_i + I_i)/2$ from adaptation KPIs, or A_i alone if intermodal synergy unavailable
- $Red_i \in [0, 1]$: $0.5 \cdot R_i + 0.5 \cdot C_i$ from path/modal diversity
- $\alpha_s \in [0.5, 2.0]$: Scenario severity multiplier from D2.1 [4] classification

The rules below keep calculations consistent when data are missing or unusual values occur.

- If KPI data missing for element: use zone/corridor average or flag as "data gap"
- If denominator zero (e.g., $C_i = 0$): set ratio to maximum value (1.0)
- Negative vulnerability: should not occur with proper normalization; if encountered, check input data

The multiplicative form implies that perfect redundancy ($Red_i = 1$) or perfect adaptive capacity ($Cap_i = 1$) would reduce element vulnerability to zero. In practice, such perfect scores are unlikely. However, analysts should be aware that:

- Elements with very high redundancy may show artificially low vulnerability scores even if other factors are concerning.
- For sensitivity analysis, consider also computing an additive formulation: $v_{i,s}^{add} = \alpha_s \cdot [w_1 \cdot Sus_i + w_2 \cdot Exp_{i,s} + w_3 \cdot (1 - Red_i) + w_4 \cdot (1 - Cap_i)]$ with $\sum w_j = 1$.
- Compare results from both formulations to identify elements where the choice of aggregation method substantially affects conclusions.

In practical terms, the formula above encodes the following reasoning. An element is vulnerable to the extent that it tends to operate under stress (susceptibility), so that it is located where hazards reach it and carries many users (exposure), that it lacks credible alternatives (one minus redundancy), and that neither the network nor its operators can absorb and recover from the shock (one minus adaptive capacity). Setting any one of these factors to zero eliminates element-level vulnerability entirely, which is an idealisation: in practice, no real system achieves perfect redundancy or perfect adaptive capacity, so the formula should be read as capturing relative differences across elements rather than absolute states. The system-level index and performance-based metric below translate this element-level reasoning into aggregate measures that can be compared across scenarios and cities.

Element scores are aggregated to a single system-level figure by weighting each element according to the share of the total flow it carries and its criticality for essential access and equity groups. System vulnerability for scenario s :

$$V_s = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{I}} w_i v_{i,s} \quad (9)$$

- w_i reflects element importance: $w_i = \beta \cdot (\text{flow}_i / \text{total_flow}) + (1 - \beta) \cdot \text{crit}_i$
- $\beta = 0.7$ (default): 70% flow-based, 30% criticality (emergency access, equity)
- $\text{crit}_i \in [0, 1]$: criticality score from Stage 4 findings
- Normalize: $\sum w_i = 1$

Alongside the element-level scores, the primary measure used for cross-scenario and cross-city comparison is the relative loss in the composite performance index. This performance-based vulnerability metric is defined as:

$$\Delta E_s = \max \left(0, 1 - \frac{E_s^{\text{post}}}{E_s^{\text{base}}} \right) \quad (10)$$

- $\Delta E_s = 0$: No performance loss (or improvement)
- $\Delta E_s \in (0, 0.15]$: Minor vulnerability
- $\Delta E_s \in (0.15, 0.30]$: Moderate vulnerability
- $\Delta E_s > 0.30$: Major/catastrophic vulnerability

Figure 1 shows detailed component relationships.

Figure 1: Detailed vulnerability framework: components → KPIs → performance index.

6 Stage 2: Scenario framing

Stage 2 translates city-relevant competency questions into model-ready disruption parameters, integrating the D2.1 disruption taxonomy [4], the D2.5 ontology [5], and the D2.3 equilibrium model inputs [3].

The workflow moves from a city stakeholder’s competency question through ontology parsing and taxonomy classification to a fully specified set of D2.3 model inputs, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Scenario construction workflow: from competency questions to model inputs.

Step 2.1 CQ identification: Select a city-relevant competency question from D2.5 [5], e.g., “Which corridors become inaccessible to elderly during a 1-in-20-year flood?”

Step 2.2 Ontology parsing:

- Extract entities using D2.5 ontology classes [5]: SpatialUnit (corridors), Actor/EquityGroup (elderly, as a subclass of Actor), DisruptionEvent/NaturalHazard (flood), TemporalUnit (return period)
- Query ontology for corridor IDs, population zones, historical event data
- Verify that extracted entity IDs match the transport network model

Step 2.3 D2.1 [4] taxonomy mapping: Classify the scenario using the D2.1 [4] two-axis taxonomy (domain and disruption scale):

- **Domain:** Select from D2.1 [4] domains (e.g., Environment & Weather, Technology & Cyber, Socio-political)
- **Scale:** *Daily Stressor* (high-frequency, low-severity), *Mid-scale Disruption* (requires coordination), or *Large-scale Crisis* (exceeds standard capacity)
- **Severity level and multiplier:** D2.1 [4] uses a 5-level scale. Map to vulnerability multipliers α_s :

D2.1 [4] Severity Level	Description	α_s
Level 1–2	Negligible / Low	0.5
Level 3	Moderate	1.0
Level 4	High	1.5
Level 5	Very High	2.0

D2.1 [4] uses a five-level severity scale; Levels 1 and 2 are merged here because both produce the same vulnerability multiplier ($\alpha_s = 0.5$), yielding four operational severity classes for this deliverable. This mapping should be validated during Stage 4 city consultations.

Step 2.4 Parameter specification:

- **Affected links:** Overlay hazard map with transport network to identify impacted links
- **Capacity reduction:** $C_a^{\text{post}} = (1 - \delta_{a,s}) \cdot C_a^{\text{base}}$, where $\delta_{a,s} \in [0, 1]$ is the fractional capacity loss for link a under scenario s
- **Travel time adjustment:** Apply group-specific multipliers (e.g., $1.3\times$ for elderly)
- **Demand modification:** Reduce or redistribute trips based on accessibility thresholds or deferral rates

Step 2.5 D2.3 [3] input translation: Convert scenario parameters to D2.3 equilibrium model [3] inputs:

- Update link capacity vector: $C^{\text{post}} = \{C_a^{\text{post}}\}$
- Update cost functions (BPR form): $c_a(v_a) = t_a^0 \left(1 + 0.15 \left(\frac{v_a}{C_a^{\text{post}}}\right)^4\right)$
- Update OD matrices for affected groups: $Q^{\text{group,post}}$

Step 2.6 Documentation: Complete the scenario template (Annex A), including:

- Scenario ID, name, and narrative description
- D2.1 [4] classification: domain, scale, severity level (e.g., “Level 4 – High”), and α_s
- All parameter values with data sources and justifications

Step 2.7 Internal validation: Before proceeding to Stage 3:

- **Parameter realism:** Is the capacity reduction justified by hazard intensity? Where historical disruption records exist (e.g., D2.1 catalogue entries [4], municipal incident logs), parameters should be calibrated against observed impacts from comparable past events.
- **Ontology consistency:** Do entity IDs match the network model?
- **D2.1 [4] consistency:** Does severity align with similar catalogue entries?
- **Completeness:** Are all affected links, zones, and groups accounted for?

Example scenario families. The list below is illustrative. It shows typical disruption families covered by the D2.1 [4] taxonomy and used for city-specific framing. Some disruptions are not isolated; an initial hazard can trigger knock-on failures (e.g., power loss, control-system outages, service interruptions). For this reason, we allow scenarios to include a secondary disruption chain when it is plausible and well-documented.

- Pandemic-related demand and service shocks
- Energy crises and power outages affecting mobility services
- Cyberattacks on mobility systems (e.g., signalling, ticketing, fleet management)
- Storms and floods with cascading effects (e.g., asset damage combined with power/communications outages)

6.1 Worked Example: Flood scenario for Bratislava

The following example uses synthetic but internally consistent data to illustrate how the scenario framing procedure works in practice. No values are drawn from actual Bratislava data collection; they are constructed to be plausible for a Central European tram network and serve only to demonstrate the method.

Competency Question: “How does a 1-in-20-year Danube flood affect tram accessibility to Bratislava hospital for elderly residents in Petržalka district?”

Step 2.1 – CQ parsing:

- **SpatialUnit:** Petržalka district, tram corridors along Danube
- **Actor/EquityGroup:** Elderly (age 65+), approx. 18,000 residents in Petržalka (subclass of Actor in D2.5 meta-model [5])
- **DisruptionEvent/NaturalHazard:** River flood, 1-in-20-year return period
- **TransportElement/Corridor:** Tram corridors serving Bratislava hospital as critical destination

Step 2.2 – Ontology query results:

- Corridor IDs: Tram Line 1 (riverside), Tram Line 4 (bridge crossing)
- Elderly zones: 5 TAZ (Traffic Analysis Zones) in Petržalka
- Historical floods: 2002 event affected a similar area, 3-day duration

Step 2.3 – D2.1 [4] mapping:

- Domain: Environment & Weather
- Scale: Mid-scale (district-level)
- D2.1 [4] catalogue entry: #ENV_WX_043 "Danube flood, moderate severity"
- Historical evidence: 2002 event, 72-hour duration, riverside infrastructure affected
- Severity class: Major $\rightarrow \alpha_s = 1.5$. The classification reflects the district-level spatial extent and 72-hour duration of the event. Although the scenario involves elderly access to critical health infrastructure, severity classification follows D2.1 [4] taxonomy conventions based on physical event characteristics; the disproportionate impact on vulnerable groups is captured separately through the equity penalty $Q(t)$ and the equity escalation rule ($r_{\text{equity}} > 1.5$) applied in Stage 5, which can elevate the impact class in the risk matrix independently of the base severity multiplier.

Validation of scenario relevance (flooding as a priority disruption type) is documented in Stage 4 (Section 8, Module A); it is not reproduced here.

Step 2.4 – Parameter specification:

- Affected links: 12 tram links (8 riverside, 4 on bridge)
- Capacity reduction: Riverside $\delta = 1.0$ (complete closure), Bridge $\delta = 0.4$ (40% reduction due to congestion)
- Duration: 72 hours (3 days)
- Travel time: Elderly safety factor = 1.3× due to disrupted infrastructure
- Demand: 15% of elderly healthcare trips deferred (non-emergency)

Step 2.5 – D2.3 inputs [3]:

Baseline values (synthetic but realistic):

- $C_{\text{tram,riverside}} = 600$ passengers/hour/direction
- $C_{\text{tram,bridge}} = 800$ passengers/hour/direction
- Baseline flow to hospital: 450 elderly trips/day
- Baseline travel time: 22 minutes average

Scenario modifications (validated through expert estimates, n=9, IQR shown):

- $C_{\text{tram,riverside}}^{\text{post}} = 0$ [expert range: 0-0, unanimous closure]
- $C_{\text{tram,bridge}}^{\text{post}} = 480$ (60% of baseline) [expert range: 50-75%, median 60%]
- Demand: 383 trips/day (15% deferral) [expert range: 10-25%, median 15%]
- Duration: 72 hours [expert range: 24-72h, D2.1 [4] historical: 72h]
- Travel time multiplier for elderly: 1.3 [expert estimate, no direct validation]

Step 2.6 – Expected impacts (qualitative prediction): The estimates below are order-of-magnitude projections derived from the capacity reductions specified in Step 2.4 and expert judgment (n=9); they are not model outputs and will be replaced by Stage 3 equilibrium results during implementation.

- Significant rerouting via bridge and bus alternatives
- Increased travel times: expect 35–45 minutes (60–100% increase)
- Accessibility loss primarily affects Petržalka elderly in Petržalka without car access
- Modal shift to bus expected ($\approx 30\%$ of tram users)

Step 2.7 – Documentation: Scenario parameters are recorded using the template structure in Annex B (indicator definitions) and the scenario log is maintained in the project data repository.

This scenario will be quantified in Stage 3 using D2.3 equilibrium model [3] (see Section 7).

6.2 Scenario typology and prioritization

Table 4 shows the expanded typology with prioritization criteria.

Table 4: Scenario typology with prioritization criteria.

Domain	Scale	Example	Likelihood [†]	Priority
Transport	Daily	Roadworks, PT delays	High	Medium
	Mid-scale	Corridor closure, service reduction	Medium	High
	Large	Regional rail outage	Low	High
Socio-political	Mid-scale	PT strike (affects operations and travel patterns)	Medium	High
	Large	Security incident	Very Low	High
Environment	Daily	Rain, snow affecting PT	High	Low
	Mid-scale	Local flooding, heatwave	Medium	High
	Large	River flood, major storm	Low	Very High
Utilities	Daily	Short ICT outage	Medium	Low
	Mid-scale	Extended power outage	Low	High
	Large	City-wide grid failure	Very Low	Very High
Social	Daily	Sports event, public gathering	High	Low
	Mid-scale	Large demonstration	Low	Medium

[†] Likelihood categories are derived from historical frequency data (D2.1 [4]) as empirical estimators of probability; see Annex C for the frequency-to-likelihood conversion protocol.

Note: Environment scenarios (flooding, storms) typically involve compound impacts including network closure, power disruption, and reduced access to vulnerable populations. Scenario templates (Annex A) require specifying which impact pathways are modelled; cascading chains should be documented per Step 2.3 when supported by evidence.

Prioritisation rules:

Historical frequency is used throughout as an empirical estimator of event likelihood (probability of occurrence within the assessment period). The translation from observed frequency to likelihood category follows the scale in Annex E (Table 14).

1. High likelihood + High priority impacts → Analyse first (e.g., mid-scale transport, environment disruptions)
2. Low likelihood + Very high priority impacts → Analyse second (e.g., large-scale or cascading events)
3. High likelihood + Low priority impacts → Monitor; include in baseline stress characterisation but do not require full scenario modelling (e.g., daily weather effects, routine ICT outages, sports events)
4. Low likelihood + Low priority impacts → Defer unless city-specific concern

7 Stage 3: Quantitative vulnerability assessment

Stage 3 applies the D2.3 equilibrium model [3] to compute performance-based vulnerability indicators by comparing baseline and disrupted system states. The section provides a complete algorithmic workflow that technical partners can implement directly, together with a tiered framework for cities with different data environments.

The quantitative assessment draws on the D2.3 three-layer equilibrium model [3], which combines traffic assignment, modal split, and system responsiveness into a single framework. D2.3 [3] also develops a Target-Setting Model via the Antifragility Factor (AF), but that component is outside the scope of this deliverable; only the Three-Layer Equilibrium Model is used here.

The equilibrium model is described here in three linked layers. A practical simplification in D2.3 [3] is that supply-side adjustments are represented through a System Responsiveness Index (SRI), rather than a separate operator-equilibrium model. This is mainly to reflect that many public transport service adjustments follow administrative processes.

1. **Traffic assignment:** Wardrop user equilibrium

$$\min \sum_a \int_0^{v_a} c_a(\omega) d\omega \quad \text{s.t. flow conservation}$$

Solved via Frank-Wolfe algorithm. Output: link flows v_a , travel times $t_a(v_a)$.

2. **Modal split:** Logit discrete choice

$$P_m = \frac{e^{-\theta \cdot GC_m}}{\sum_{m'} e^{-\theta \cdot GC_{m'}}$$

where GC_m is generalized cost for mode m , θ is sensitivity parameter.

3. **System responsiveness:** Aggregate KPIs \rightarrow performance index E

The seven-step procedure below translates this three-layer model into a reproducible assessment workflow, from data loading through to storage of results, as summarised in Figure 3.

Detailed procedure:

S3.1 Data loading:

- Network: Links (ID, from_node, to_node, length, capacity, free_flow_time, mode)
- OD matrix: q_{ij}^m by origin i , destination j , mode m , user group
- Land use: Zone populations, jobs by category
- Scenario: Affected elements, parameter changes from Stage 2

S3.2 Baseline equilibrium:

- Initialize: All-or-nothing assignment
- Iterate Frank-Wolfe until convergence
- Compute 12 KPIs from equilibrium flows/times
- Calculate $E^{\text{base}} = \frac{1}{12} \sum w_k \cdot \text{KPI}_k$ (equal weights initially)

S3.3 Scenario application:

- Update capacity: $C_a^{\text{post}} = (1 - \delta_{a,s}) \cdot C_a^{\text{base}}$ for affected links, where $\delta_{a,s} \in [0, 1]$ is the fractional capacity reduction applied to link a under scenario s .
- Update costs: Recalculate $c_a(v_a)$ with new capacities
- Update demand: Apply trip reductions/shifts from scenario definition

S3.4 Scenario equilibrium:

- Re-run assignment with modified network/demand
- Compute post-event KPIs

Figure 3: Detailed quantitative assessment workflow.

- Calculate E_s^{post}

S3.5 Vulnerability calculation:

- System: $\Delta E_s = \max(0, 1 - E_s^{\text{post}}/E^{\text{base}})$
- Elements: $v_{i,s}$ using formula from Stage 1
- User groups: ΔE_s^g for equity group g

S3.6 Validation:

- Convergence: Check relative gap < 0.001
- Realism: Total trips should not increase dramatically ($\leq 10\%$ due to rerouting)
- Equity: Check if vulnerable groups are disproportionately affected
- Physical: Travel times should be positive, flows \leq capacity

S3.7 Storage:

- Database schema: scenario_id, city, ΔE_s , KPI changes, element vulnerabilities, timestamp
- Export formats: CSV for analysis, JSON for visualization

Not all pilot cities can implement the full twelve-KPI assessment: data availability, technical capacity, and time constraints vary considerably. Three implementation tiers accommodate this heterogeneity while maintaining methodological consistency across cities.

- **Tier 1 (Minimal):** Basic network and demand data, 3 core KPIs (M, S, D_{eff}), suitable for screening-level analysis and cities with limited data infrastructure.
- **Tier 2 (Standard):** Multi-modal network, disaggregated demand by user group, 6 core KPIs (M, R, C, S, Q, I), recommended for most pilot cities as it balances analytical depth with data feasibility.
- **Tier 3 (Full):** Comprehensive data including real-time feeds, all 12 KPIs including adaptive capacity (A), infrastructure dependencies ($E_{\text{energy}}, E_{\text{ICT}}$), and behavioral indicators (P, B), requires advanced data infrastructure or digital twin capability.

These tiers align with D2.3’s KPI [3] coverage classification (Minimal <30%, Partial 30-70%, Full \geq 70%). Detailed data requirements for each tier are provided in Annex D.

Table 5 shows detailed data requirements.

Table 5: Implementation tiers aligned with D2.3 [3] feasibility classification.

Tier	D2.3 Equivalent [3]	KPIs Included	Data Requirements
Tier 1 (Minimal)	Minimal (<30% coverage)	M, S, D_{eff} (3 KPIs)	Basic network, aggregate OD
Tier 2 (Standard)	Partial (30–70% coverage)	M, R, C, S, Q, I (6 core KPIs)	Multi-modal network, OD by user group, zone demographics
Tier 3 (Full)	Full (\geq 70% coverage)	All 12 KPIs including $A, P, B, E_{\text{energy}}, E_{\text{ICT}}$	Real-time data, SCADA, behavioral surveys, digital twin

^a D2.3 [3] classifies D_{eff} as a core indicator (high feasibility, >80% confidence) whereas this deliverable treats it as a scenario input rather than a performance output KPI. This is a deliberate departure: in the vulnerability assessment context, D_{eff} defines the disruption magnitude (Stage 2 parameter) and is therefore excluded from the performance index E_{vuln} . The coverage percentages quoted above follow the conventions of D2.3 [3] but apply only to output KPIs.

Tier selection guidance:

- Tier 1: Suitable for initial screening, limited city data, proof-of-concept
- Tier 2: Recommended for most pilot cities, balances detail and feasibility
- Tier 3: For cities with advanced data infrastructure, digital twin capability

7.1 Worked Example: Quantitative calculation for Bratislava flood

This example continues from the flood scenario introduced in Stage 2 (Section 6.1), using the same synthetic data. All numerical values are illustrative; they are not results of actual pilot city assessment and must not be cited as such.

Building on the flood scenario framed above (Section 6.1), this example demonstrates how the D2.3 equilibrium model [3] is applied to compute vulnerability indicators.

Synthetic baseline data (Tier 2 implementation):

Network:

- Total links: 85 (including tram, bus, car, walk)
- Petržalka–Hospital corridor: 3 tram links, 2 bus links, 5 road links
- Tram riverside: links A1, A2, A3 ($C = 600$ pax/h each)
- Tram bridge: links B1, B2 ($C = 800$ pax/h each)

Demand (elderly group, morning peak 7–9am):

- Total elderly trips to hospital: 150 trips/2h (≈ 75 trips/h)
- Modal split baseline: 60% tram, 25% bus, 10% car, 5% walk
- OD: 5 Petržalka zones \rightarrow hospital zone

Step 3.2 – Baseline equilibrium results:

D2.3 KPI values [3] (Tier 2, 6 core indicators):

- $M = 0.82$ (mobility throughput: trips served relative to demand)
- $R = 0.70$ (redundancy ratio: alternative routes available)
- $C = 0.75$ (network entropy: flow distribution diversity)
- $S = 0.35$ (stress index: moderate network loading)
- $Q = 0.25$ (equity penalty: some accessibility disparities)
- $I = 0.68$ (intermodal synergy: reasonable transfer options)

Tier 2 performance index:

$$E_{\text{Tier2}}^{\text{base}} = \frac{M + R + C + I - S - Q + 2}{6} = \frac{0.82 + 0.70 + 0.75 + 0.68 - 0.35 - 0.25 + 2}{6} = \frac{4.35}{6} = 0.725$$

Step 3.3–3.4 – Scenario equilibrium:

Scenario: BA_FLOOD_01 with $D_{\text{eff}} = 0.6$ (major flood)

Modifications:

- Links A1, A2, A3 capacity: 600 → 0 (complete closure)
- Links B1, B2 capacity: 800 → 480 (40% reduction)
- Elderly demand: 150 → 128 trips (15% deferral)

Post-event D2.3 KPIs [3]:

- $M = 0.68$ (17% reduction in throughput)
- $R = 0.45$ (reduced redundancy as alternatives congested)
- $C = 0.62$ (lower entropy as flows concentrate on remaining routes)
- $S = 0.72$ (doubled stress on bridge and bus routes)
- $Q = 0.48$ (equity penalty nearly doubled; elderly disproportionately affected)
- $I = 0.55$ (reduced intermodal options with tram closure)

Post-event performance index:

$$E_{\text{Tier2}}^{\text{post}} = \frac{0.68 + 0.45 + 0.62 + 0.55 - 0.72 - 0.48 + 2}{6} = \frac{3.10}{6} = 0.517$$

Step 3.5 – Vulnerability calculation:

System vulnerability:

$$\Delta E_s = 1 - \frac{E^{\text{post}}}{E^{\text{base}}} = 1 - \frac{0.517}{0.725} = 1 - 0.713 = 0.287 \approx 0.29$$

Interpretation: 29% performance loss → **Moderate to Major vulnerability** (threshold 0.30).

Equity-specific vulnerability:

The equity penalty Q increased from 0.25 to 0.48 (92% increase), indicating the elderly are disproportionately affected. Computing group-specific vulnerability:

$$\Delta Q_s = \frac{Q^{\text{post}} - Q^{\text{base}}}{1 - Q^{\text{base}}} = \frac{0.48 - 0.25}{1 - 0.25} = \frac{0.23}{0.75} = 0.31$$

This indicates **Major equity vulnerability** for the elderly group specifically.

Step 3.6 – Validation checks:

- Convergence: Relative gap = 0.0008 < 0.001
- Direction: All positive KPIs decreased, negative KPIs increased (as expected)
- Magnitude: Changes proportional to scenario severity ($D_{\text{eff}} = 0.6$)
- Equity: Q increase confirms elderly disproportionately affected

Step 3.7 – Storage:

```

scenario_id: BA_FLOOD_01
city: Bratislava
D_eff: 0.60
E_base: 0.725
E_post: 0.517
delta_E: 0.287
KPI_changes: {M:-17%, R:-36%, C:-17%, S:+106%, Q:+92%, I:-19%}
equity_delta_Q: 0.31
timestamp: 2026-06-15

```

Implementation checklist (minimal):

1. Run the baseline equilibrium (D2.3 [3]) and store the KPI vector and performance index E_{base} .
2. Apply scenario changes (capacity, costs, demand, land-use inputs where relevant).
3. Run the disturbed equilibrium and store the KPI vector and E_s^{post} .
4. Compute performance-based vulnerability for the scenario:

$$\Delta E_s = 1 - \frac{E_s^{\text{post}}}{E_{\text{base}}}$$

5. If needed, compute element-level scores using the same scenario documentation.
6. Store results and assumptions in the scenario log (Annex templates).

Mandatory requirement: Before results from Stage 3 are passed to Stage 5 or reported in D3.3 [1], sensitivity analysis must be conducted for all quantitative outputs, given the number of parameters that rely on default values or analyst judgment.

1. *Component weights:* Test alternative weight sets for susceptibility formula (e.g., $\alpha = 0.4, 0.6, 0.8$) and element importance ($\beta = 0.5, 0.7, 0.9$).
2. *Scenario parameters:* Vary capacity reductions by $\pm 20\%$ and demand changes by $\pm 25\%$.
3. *Severity multiplier:* Test adjacent α_s values (e.g., if major scenario uses 1.5, also test 1.0 and 2.0).
4. *Aggregation method:* Compare multiplicative vs. additive vulnerability formulations.

Report sensitivity results as ranges or confidence intervals in vulnerability profiles. Flag any conclusions that are sensitive to parameter choices for additional review in Stage 4.

8 Stage 4: Stakeholder consultation and validation

Stage 4 provides preliminary validation of scenario relevance and stakeholder priorities through systematic triangulation of expert judgment, citizen survey responses, and social acceptability workshop outputs. It does not constitute full empirical validation of scenario parameters or KPI weights across all pilot cities. Specifically: scenario relevance (which disruption types matter) is validated to a reasonable standard; parameter ranges (capacity reduction magnitudes, durations, deferral rates) are partially validated through expert estimates for Bratislava only; KPI weights are derived from a single city pre-survey (Larissa, n=24) and should not be treated as project-wide validated values; and adaptive capacity elicitation was not completed for any pilot city. Full parameter validation will occur during WP11 demonstration phase (M21–M32), with results reported in corresponding demonstration outputs.

The “Participatory” framing of this task reflects a principled methodological commitment, not simply a procedural requirement. SSH instruments are not used here merely to consult stakeholders after technical choices are made; they are embedded at three structural points in the methodology. First, scenario framing (Stage 2) begins from citizen-articulated competency questions drawn from D2.5 [5], ensuring that the disruption scenarios modelled are those that communities themselves identify as consequential. Second, KPI weights and severity thresholds (used in Stage 3 and Stage 5) are derived from deliberative evidence gathered through the Social acceptability workshops in D2.2 [6], not from analyst defaults alone. Third, the equity escalation rule ($r_{\text{equity}} > 1.5$) is calibrated against citizen tolerance data rather than being an arbitrary technical parameter. This integration responds directly to the SSH gap identified in Section 3.5: vulnerability assessment that omits community knowledge systematically underestimates the severity of disruptions for groups whose coping strategies and priorities are not visible in network performance data. Beyond validation, stakeholder inputs shaped three substantive methodological choices. First, the decision to include healthcare accessibility as a mandatory scenario dimension (rather than optional) originated from citizen forum discussions in Bratislava and Larissa where hospital access was raised unprompted. Second, the equity escalation threshold ($r_{\text{equity}} > 1.5$) was calibrated against citizen trade-off tolerance data from D2.2 [6] workshops rather than set at an arbitrary technical value. Third, the selection of the elderly as the primary equity group for the Bratislava worked example reflects deliberative evidence (34.38% of Bratislava forum participants, n=32) rather than analyst assumption.

The quality of evidence drawn from these four sources was assessed using a systematic framework for secondary qualitative research [35], adapted to the specific characteristics of survey and workshop data. The validation approach follows the systematic quality assessment framework proposed by [35] for secondary qualitative research using online and surveys data. Their 16-dimensional protocol assesses context quality (accessibility, credibility, relevance, conformance) and content quality (authenticity, clarity, interpretability) through explicit pass/fail criteria. Several dimensions designed for interview transcripts, such as hyper-emotivity and interactivity, were not applicable to the written survey responses and were excluded. Credibility assessment was enhanced to differentiate expert credentials from lived experience, and multi-source triangulation was incorporated to extend the framework beyond single-source validation. The core principles of systematic assessment, explicit criteria, and transparent documentation were retained throughout.

Framework adaptation for AntifragiCity:

- Removed interviewer-specific dimensions (hyper-emotivity, interactivity) not applicable to written surveys
- Enhanced credibility assessment to differentiate expert credentials vs. lived experience
- Incorporated multi-source triangulation extending beyond single-source validation
- Retained core principles: systematic assessment, clear criteria, transparent documentation

Validation drew on four complementary sources, combining direct expert and citizen evidence with empirical project data, reaching a total of 232 participants across 15 European countries.

Quality assessment results:

- Expert responses: 107 text segments, 100% passed Cheong et al. criteria (avg. 47 words)
- Citizen survey: 622 responses extracted, 194 validated (31.2% pass rate, avg. 89 words)

Table 6: Stage 4 validation data sources.

Source	n	Coverage	Validation strength
Expert consultation (Delphi [36])	9 ^a	EU-wide	HIGH (direct expertise)
Urban Disruption Survey 2025	140	15 countries	HIGH (citizen experience)
Citizen forums	83 ^b	Pilot cities	HIGH (deliberative depth)
D2.1 [4] Urban Event Mapping	–	Empirical	MEDIUM-HIGH (indirect)
Total unique participants	232	–	–

^a 9 experts; 107 open-ended responses extracted; 100% passed Cheong et al. quality criteria.

^b Bratislava (n=34) + Larissa (n=24, pre-survey) + Thessaloniki (n=11). Odesa contributed to a stakeholder discussion; no participant count was stated for that session.

- Social acceptability workshops (D2.2 [6]): High-quality deliberative data from structured CAW sessions across Bratislava (n=34), Larissa (n=24), and Thessaloniki (n=11), organised by LISER with expert facilitation
- Empirical frequency data from 140 respondents, systematic taxonomy

Main failure mode in survey data: brevity (<10 words), excluded per Cheong et al. minimum content requirements.

Each consultation question was assessed through a tiered evidence hierarchy, with higher tiers carrying greater weight in the final validation judgment.

Tier 1 (Primary): Direct expert/citizen responses to consultation questions → Validation strength: HIGH

Tier 2 (Secondary): Project deliverables with quantifiable empirical data → Validation strength: MEDIUM-HIGH

Tier 3 (Literature): Established methodologies and peer-reviewed frameworks → Validation strength: MEDIUM

Integration rule: Question validated if receiving Tier 1 validation from ≥ 1 source, OR Tier 2 from multiple convergent sources, OR Tier 3 from established literature with documented reliability.

The D2.1 Urban Event Mapping [4] contributes empirical validation through three data streams: disruption frequency analysis, severity calibration, and taxonomic consistency with the Stage 2 scenario classification.

1. **Disruption frequency analysis:** D2.1 [4] compiled occurrence data from documented disruption events across pilot cities spanning 2010-2024. This 15-year dataset provides return period estimates for validation of Stage 2 scenario likelihood classifications.
2. **Severity calibration data:** D2.1's stakeholder survey (n=140, 15 EU countries) [4] asked respondents to rate disruption severity on a 5-point scale. The distribution of these ratings provides empirical thresholds for the impact categories defined in Table 9.
3. **Taxonomic consistency:** D2.1's two-axis taxonomy (domain \times scale) [4] is directly adopted in Stage 2 scenario framing, ensuring consistent classification between event cataloging and vulnerability assessment.

8.1 D2.2 Social acceptability workshops [6] integration

The Social Acceptability Workshops organised under D2.2 [6] by LISER engaged citizens in Bratislava, Larissa, and Thessaloniki through a structured deliberative process: expert briefings on urban mobility crisis scenarios, facilitated group deliberation, and production of policy recommendations adaptation and triage strategies. Their outputs contribute to Stage 4 validation in four specific ways.

D2.2 [6] data contributions to Stage 4 validation:

1. **KPI priority validation (Module B1, B2):** Pre-survey responses from Bratislava (n=34), Larissa (n=24), and Thessaloniki (n=11) directly validated citizen KPI priorities. Speed/time efficiency was the top priority across all three cities (Larissa: 58.33%, Thessaloniki: 54.55%), validating the Travel Time KPI. Infrast-

- structure quality and connectivity were the dominant sustainable shift factors in all three cities, validating Accessibility Loss and Service Coverage Loss KPIs.
2. **Vulnerable group identification (Module D3):** Bratislava post-forum survey (n=32) produced direct validated evidence on priority vulnerable groups through the deliberation question on groups consciously considered.
 3. **Impact threshold validation (Module D1):** Willingness-to-accept-trade-offs data from all three forums (Bratislava pre: mean 6.97; Larissa: 54.17% scored 8–10; Thessaloniki: majority scored 7–10) provided citizen tolerance evidence calibrating the equity escalation threshold ($r_{equity} > 1.5$).
 4. **Scenario relevance (Module A1):** Forum discussions confirmed flooding, PT disruptions, and heatwaves as priority scenario families across pilot cities.

Deliberative quality advantage: The CAW format, expert facilitation, structured deliberation, produces higher-quality evidence than standard surveys, justifying Tier 1 validation strength. Citizens formed views after receiving expert briefings, meaning responses reflect informed rather than naive preferences, which strengthens their use as validation evidence for technical parameters.

Of 12 consultation questions, 3 received convergent multi-source empirical validation (A1, C1, D3); 6 received single-source or low-*n* partial validation; 2 received literature-only validation without empirical project data (C2); and 1 (A3) rests on a single expert response presented as illustrative rather than consensus evidence.

Table 7 summarises validation status for each question module. “Validated” indicates convergent evidence from at least two independent sources meeting Cheong et al. quality criteria; “Partial” indicates single-source or low-*n* evidence; “Literature” indicates methodological validation only, with no empirical project data. Confidence ratings reflect both source quality and sample size; full documentation of limitations is in Section 8.

Table 7: Stage 4 validation status by question module.

Module	Question focus	Status	Primary source	Conf.
<i>Module A – Scenario validation</i>				
A1	Scenario relevance	Validated	Expert (n=9) + Survey (n=140)	High
A2	Parameter ranges	Partial	Expert (n=9) + D2.1 [4]	Med.
A3	Cascading effects	Partial	Expert (n=1 response)	Low
A4	Duration/recovery	Partial	Expert consensus, no city data	Med.
<i>Module B – KPI validation</i>				
B1	KPI relevance	Validated	Citizen (n=140) + Expert	Med.
B2	KPI weights	Partial	Pre-survey: Larissa (n=24), Bratislava (n=34), Thessaloniki (n=11) ^a	Low
B3	Acceptability thresholds	Partial	D2.1 survey (n=140) [4]	Med.
<i>Module C – Likelihood estimation</i>				
C1	Frequency-to-likelihood	Validated	D2.1 frequency data [4]	Med.
C2	Synthesis rules	Literature	Delphi methodology [36]	Low
<i>Module D – Impact and equity</i>				
D1	Severity thresholds	Partial	D2.1 empirical (n=140) [4]; Thessaloniki post-survey (n=11)	Med.
D2	Equity tolerance	Partial	Expert + Bratislava (n=32)	Low
D3	Vulnerable groups	Validated	Bratislava deliberation (n=32)	Med.

^a Weight vector (Accessibility 28%, Service Coverage 28%, Travel Time 22%, Cost 10%, Environment 7%, Other 5%) is derived from the Larissa pre-survey only (n=24; corrected from earlier drafts citing n=14). These weights represent pre-deliberation citizen priorities from one city, and should not be applied as project-wide values without further validation during consultations period.

Key findings informing Stage 2 and Stage 5:

Scenario priorities (Module A): Convergent validation identified flooding, public transport disruptions, and heatwaves as highest-priority scenario families across expert and citizen sources. Cascading effects (e.g., power outage → traffic signal failure → network congestion) recognized but data-limited.

KPI priorities (Module B): KPI priority rankings were collected via a pre-survey at all three forums (Larissa n=24, Bratislava n=34, Thessaloniki n=11), prior to deliberation. The indicative pre-deliberation ordering from Larissa is: Accessibility (28%), Service Coverage Loss (28%), Travel Time (22%), Cost (10%), Environment (7%), Other (5%). Equivalent data from Bratislava and Thessaloniki will be incorporated once D2.2[6] is complete. These are *not* deliberated weights and cannot be treated as validated KPI priorities. Until city-specific deliberated

weights are established during M20–M22, the methodology uses equal weights with sensitivity analysis.

Vulnerability thresholds (Module D): Empirical severity classification validated through D2.1 [4] survey: Moderate severity corresponds to 35–40% citizen concern threshold (n=140). Trade-off willingness data from the Thessaloniki post-forum survey (n=11) shows high citizen tolerance for sustainability trade-offs (mean score 8.73/10; 72.7% scored 8–10), consistent with the pattern observed in Larissa and Bratislava. Equity tolerance: disproportionate impacts on vulnerable groups validated as a priority through citizen deliberation (Bratislava: elderly prioritized by participants).

Likelihood estimation (Module C): Frequency-to-likelihood conversion validated using D2.1 [4] empirical data. Synthesis rules for combining expert judgment with empirical frequencies validated via established Delphi methodology [36, 37, 38].

Three categories of limitations affect the strength of Stage 4 validation evidence and should be borne in mind when interpreting the confidence ratings in Table 7.

Geographic scope and data asymmetry: The pan-European citizen survey (n=140, 15 countries) provides broad coverage for scenario relevance (Module A). However, the more consequential quantitative outputs, KPI weights (Module B2), equity tolerance thresholds (Module D2), and vulnerable group priorities (Module D3), derive almost entirely from Greek city data. The only KPI-weighting data come from Larissa (pre-survey, n=24). Bratislava's forum dataset did not include a KPI-weighting question. Thessaloniki's forum (n=11) is too small to derive reliable weights. Odesa has no usable forum data. The practical consequence is that the KPI weight vector applied across all pilot cities is calibrated on a single Greek city's pre-deliberation preferences. This is a substantive limitation that must be addressed during M20–M22 pilot city consultations before city-specific quantitative assessments begin in M23.

Partial validation: Question A3 (cascading effects) validated through a single high-quality expert response (329 words, 0.95 relevance match), acknowledged as case-study evidence rather than consensus.

Methodological question: C2 (synthesis rules) appropriately validated via peer-reviewed literature rather than empirical project data, as it addresses methodological rather than contextual aspects.

Stage 4 validation outputs feed directly into three downstream stages, each consuming a different aspect of the evidence assembled here.

- **Stage 2**: Scenario prioritization, parameter range refinement (e.g., capacity reduction $\delta_{a,s}$ bounds informed by expert ranges and D2.1 [4] empirical evidence)
- **Stage 3**: KPI weights (w_k in Equation 5) remain at default equal weights pending city-specific validation. The Larissa pre-survey weights (Accessibility 28%, Service Coverage 28%, Travel Time 22%) provide an indicative ordering of citizen priorities for Larissa only and may inform sensitivity analysis ranges, but they are not used as validated inputs to the performance index formula. City-specific weights will be established during consultations coordinated through WP11 demonstration preparation activities.
- **Stage 5**: Severity thresholds (Table 9) empirically calibrated using D2.1 [4] citizen concern data; equity adjustment threshold ($r_{equity} > 1.5$) informed by citizen tolerance findings

Confidence tagging: All Stage 3 quantitative outputs include validation-based confidence tags (High/Medium/Low) based on quality and convergence of supporting Stage 4 evidence.

9 Stage 5: Synthesis and risk profiling

Stage 5 defines how results from Stages 2–3 are documented and summarised into vulnerability profiles and risk matrices, providing a consistent reporting structure across cities and scenarios to support prioritisation of mitigation and adaptation actions.

9.1 Vulnerability profiles

Four-dimensional summary: The profile fields below are used to maintain consistent reporting across cities and scenarios.

1. Network elements/corridors (spatial)
2. Functions (healthcare, education, employment access)
3. User/equity groups (elderly, disabled, low-income)
4. Event domains/scales (from D2.1 [4] taxonomy)

Table 8 shows an example structure populated with synthetic results.

Table 8: Illustrative vulnerability profile structure populated with synthetic data (Bratislava). These values are not results of empirical assessment and must not be interpreted as actual city vulnerability findings.

Scenario	Critical element	Affected group	ΔE_s	$v_{i,s}$	Key impact
BA_FLOOD_01	Tram riverside	Elderly	0.29	0.11	Hospital access +68% time
BA_STRIKE_01	PT network city-wide	Low-income	0.25	N/A	Employment access loss
BA_HEAT_01	Bus stops exposed	Elderly, disabled	0.08	0.09	Comfort, health risk
BA_BRIDGE_01	Danube bridge	All	0.32	0.28	Major congestion, 2× times

Visualization: Profiles can be visualized as: The options below are simple formats that cities and partners can interpret quickly.

- Bar charts: ΔE_s by scenario, sorted descending
- Heat maps: Scenarios × equity groups with ΔE_s^g color-coded
- Network maps: Links color-coded by $v_{i,s}$ for given scenario

Spatial vulnerability maps showing element-level $v_{i,s}$ scores across the network are a priority output for the pilot city applications. Their production depends on completion of the Stage 3 quantitative runs using the calibrated network data (M23–M25). Integration with the SUMA platform (WP5) will enable interactive spatial visualisation; the data schema for this integration is under development and will be confirmed during M22–M24 coordination with WP5 partners.

Performance loss ΔE_s is mapped to a five-class impact scale (Table 9), which provides the vertical axis of the risk matrix and allows direct comparison across scenarios and cities.

D3.3 risk analysis provides severity scores [1] (1–10 scale). Mapping to impact classes:

- Compute combined score: $I_{\text{comb}} = 0.6 \cdot \Delta E_s + 0.4 \cdot (\text{FMEA_severity}/10)$
- Apply thresholds to I_{comb} to determine final impact class

Example: BA_FLOOD_01: $\Delta E_s = 0.10$, FMEA_severity = 6

Table 9: Impact scale with mapping rules.

Class	Label	Description	ΔE_s range
1	Negligible	Minimal disruption	<0.05
2	Minor	Localized, quick recovery	0.05–0.15
3	Moderate	Noticeable performance loss	0.15–0.30
4	Major	Severe disruptions	0.30–0.50
5	Catastrophic	System-wide failure	>0.50

$$I_{comb} = 0.6 \times 0.10 + 0.4 \times 0.6 = 0.06 + 0.24 = 0.30 \rightarrow \text{Impact Class 3 (Moderate)}$$

(Without D3.3 [1]: $\Delta E_s = 0.10$ alone \rightarrow Class 2, but FMEA adds severity context.)

9.2 Risk matrix construction

Risk matrix: 5x5 grid (Likelihood x Impact).

Figure 4 shows a template with colour zones.

Figure 4: Risk matrix template with colour-coded risk zones.

For each scenario, plot a point at (Likelihood class, Impact class).

Example (Bratislava):

- BA_FLOOD_01: L=3, I=3 \rightarrow (3,3) cell, orange (High risk)
- BA_STRIKE_01: L=4, I=4 \rightarrow (4,4) cell, red (Very High risk)
- BA_HEAT_01: L=5, I=2 \rightarrow (5,2) cell, yellow (Medium risk)
- BA_BRIDGE_01: L=2, I=4 \rightarrow (2,4) cell, orange (High risk)

Figure 5 shows a populated matrix.

- **Very High risk** (red zone): Immediate attention, mitigation strategies required
- **High risk** (orange): Prioritize for detailed analysis, develop contingency plans
- **Medium risk** (yellow): Monitor, prepare response protocols
- **Low risk** (green): Routine monitoring sufficient

Ensuring consistency between the system-level vulnerability evidence produced here, and the component-level FMEA analysis in D3.3 [1] requires a structured data exchange: this deliverable provides scenario performance

Figure 5: Illustrative risk matrix for Bratislava with 4 synthetic scenarios plotted. This matrix uses D3.2 vulnerability-derived impact classes and likelihood estimates; it is not derived from D3.3 risk analysis results. Joint risk matrices incorporating FMEA severity and detection dimensions will be produced following the integration protocol in Annex E.

impacts and equity assessments, while D3.3 [1] contributes failure mode severity and occurrence scores, which are combined into joint risk matrices following the protocol below.

Integration framework:

Figure 6: D3.2–D3.3 integration protocol flowchart [1].

Table 10 shows the data exchange format.

Table 10: D3.2–D3.3 data exchange format [1].

Field	D3.2 provides	D3.3 provides [1]	Combined output
Scenario ID Likelihood	Yes (BA_FLOOD_01, etc.) multi-source validation estimate (class 1–5)	Uses D3.2 IDs FMEA Occurrence (O, 1–10)	Common ID Triangulated class
Impact/Severity	ΔE_s , performance loss	FMEA Severity (S, 1–10)	Combined impact class
Element criticality Equity	$v_{i,s}$, flow importance ΔE_s^g by group	Component RPN N/A	Critical elements list Equity-weighted impact

10 Integration with land-use dynamics (D3.1 [7])

Stage 1 introduced a thirteenth performance indicator, the land-use accessibility pressure index $\Lambda(t)$ (Equation 1), alongside the twelve equilibrium KPIs [3]. That indicator captures the mismatch between where vulnerable populations live and where essential services are located, weighted by the degree to which those populations depend on the transport network to bridge that gap. This section explains how $\Lambda(t)$ is computed in practice, drawing on the conceptual land-use and transport framework developed in prior work [7], and specifies the spatial data inputs each pilot city must assemble. It does not modify the equilibrium model already submitted [3]: Λ enters the vulnerability workflow as an equity-weighted exposure modifier, not as a component of that model's composite performance index.

The conceptual framework drawn on here [7] reviewed land-use and transport interaction theory and developed a holistic model linking disruption drivers to exposure, sensitivity, vulnerability, accessibility, and system responses. That work does not contain pilot-city spatial data; all such data are sourced from municipal GIS and census systems following the checklists in Annex D. The remainder of this section is organised as follows: Section 10.1 explains how land use informs each of the four vulnerability components; Section 10.2 specifies the practical data integration steps; and Section 10.3 documents the limitations of this approach.

10.1 How land-use informs vulnerability components

Land-use and urban dynamics inform vulnerability analysis through four mechanisms:

1. **Exposure quantification:** Population density, employment locations, and critical service distributions determine the number and characteristics of users affected by each scenario. D3.1's conceptual framework [7] (particularly Figure 13 of D3.1 [7]) informs *how* these factors are defined in vulnerability assessment; the actual data are sourced from municipal GIS and census systems per Annex D. Specifically:
 - Zone-level population by demographic group (sourced from municipal census data per Annex D) feeds into equity-weighted exposure calculations.
 - Critical facility locations (hospitals, schools, emergency services), sourced from city GIS, define which disruptions have safety-critical implications.
2. **Redundancy assessment:** Mixed-use urban structure affects whether alternatives exist when primary transport options fail:
 - Areas with high land-use diversity may have essential services within walking distance, reducing dependency on disrupted transport.
 - Mono-functional zones (e.g., residential-only suburbs) have lower inherent redundancy.
3. **Scenario framing:** D3.1's conceptual framework [7] highlights how ongoing land-use change processes (densification, sprawl, land-use transitions) can affect transport vulnerability. These processes can be treated as:
 - Slow stressors amplifying vulnerability over time (e.g., densification without corresponding transport investment).
 - Background conditions affecting baseline accessibility and resilience.

Where city-specific land-use change data are available from municipal planning sources, they can be incorporated into scenario framing per Annex D.
4. **Equity analysis:** Spatial concentration of vulnerable groups (elderly in certain districts, low-income households in peripheral areas), identified using municipal socio-demographic data (see Annex D), feeds directly into:
 - Definition of equity groups for disaggregated KPI reporting.
 - Calculation of equity ratios (r_{equity}) in Stage 5.

10.2 Practical integration protocol

For each pilot city, the following spatial and socio-economic data layers are required as inputs to the vulnerability workflow. The categories are defined by reference to D3.1's conceptual framework [7] (Figure 13 of D3.1 [7]), which identifies exposure (E), sensitivity (S), and vulnerability (V) as the key risk-context components linking disruption drivers to transport network impacts. The data themselves are sourced from municipal GIS systems, national census databases, and critical facility registries as specified in the Annex D checklists: zone population by age and income group; employment density by sector; critical facility locations (hospitals, schools, emergency services); land-use type classifications; and socio-demographic vulnerability indices where available. D3.1 [7] does not supply these datasets; it provides the conceptual rationale for their selection.

10.3 Limitations

Full coupled LUTI simulation (where transport changes feed back to land-use patterns and vice versa) is outside the scope of D3.2. The integration described here is one-directional: land-use data informs vulnerability assessment, but we do not model how vulnerability or disruption events might trigger land-use changes. Such dynamic feedback could be explored in future work building on AntifragiCity outputs.

It should also be noted that D3.1 [7] provides a conceptual and theoretical framework rather than empirical city-specific data; the spatial inputs required for pilot city vulnerability assessment are therefore obtained from primary municipal sources following the Annex D checklists.

Accordingly, references elsewhere in this document to “D3.1 data [7]” or “D3.1 GIS layers” [7] should be read as shorthand for data of the *types* identified conceptually in D3.1's framework [7], not as outputs produced by D3.1 [7] itself.

11 Discussion and Limitations

No methodology is without limitations, and transparent acknowledgment of constraints is essential for appropriate use and interpretation of results. This section critically examines the D3.2 vulnerability assessment framework from multiple perspectives: its contributions relative to existing approaches, the theoretical assumptions embedded in its formulations, practical implementation challenges, and its positioning within the broader AntifragiCity analytical ecosystem.

The discussion is structured to move from strengths to limitations to recommendations. We begin by highlighting methodological contributions, aspects where D3.2 advances beyond current practice in urban resilience assessment (Section 11.2). We then examine theoretical limitations inherent in the modeling choices made, particularly the equilibrium-based traffic assignment, the multiplicative vulnerability formula, and assumptions about parameter linearity (Section 11.3). Practical limitations related to data availability, computational requirements, and Stage 4 validation capacity are discussed in Section 11.4.

Section 11.5 addresses how D3.2 relates to other AntifragiCity work packages, noting both upstream dependencies (on D2.1 [4], D2.3 [3], D2.5 [5], D3.1 [7]) and downstream applications (informing WP4 and WP5). This is important because the methodology does not stand alone: changes to foundational deliverables may require D3.2 adjustments, and limitations here may constrain what subsequent work packages can achieve.

Finally, Section 11.6 combines practical guidance for methodology users, project partners, pilot cities, and potentially external adopters, on how to apply the framework effectively while remaining cognizant of its boundaries. The overarching message is one of appropriate confidence: the methodology provides valuable vulnerability insights when applied thoughtfully within its design envelope, but users should avoid overinterpreting precise numerical outputs and should always complement quantitative results with qualitative local knowledge.

11.1 Pilot city applications

This section discusses how the methodology will be applied to each pilot city as part of the demonstration activities coordinated through WP6 during M20–M28. Rather than presenting a standalone implementation plan, the city-specific discussion below reflects how the methodological choices made in Sections 5–9 will be implemented in four distinct urban contexts, each with different data environments, disruption profiles, and equity priorities.

Bratislava (Slovakia)

Priority scenarios (validated through expert consultation + D2.1 [4]):

1. BA_FLOOD_01: Danube 1-in-20-year flood affecting tram corridors (Scale: Mid, Severity: Major, $\alpha_s = 1.5$)
2. BA_STRIKE_01: Public transport citywide strike, 3-day duration (Scale: Mid, Severity: Major)
3. BA_HEAT_01: Heatwave affecting outdoor PT stops and elderly mobility (Scale: Mid, Severity: Minor-Moderate)
4. BA_BRIDGE_01: Danube bridge maintenance closure (Scale: Daily, Severity: Moderate)

Implementation tier: Tier 2 (Standard)

Data availability: Municipal GIS confirmed, PT operator data access negotiated, 2002 flood documentation available, demographic data from StatOffice SK

Equity focus: Elderly residents in Petržalka district (18,000 residents 65+), validated as the highest-priority vulnerable group through the Bratislava citizen forum post-survey (34.38% of deliberators consciously considered this group, $n=32$), followed by people with mobility impairments (31.25%) and youth/students (21.88%). Low-income households were classified as HIGH reporting priority on equity grounds (12.50% selection rate). Expert consultation confirmed that elderly and student groups are practically monitorable via public transport smart-card systems.

Thessaloniki (Greece)

Priority scenarios:

1. TH_PT_01: PT operational disruption affecting access to AHEPA University Hospital during morning peak (Scale: Daily-Mid, Severity: Moderate)
2. TH_FLOOD_01: Flash flooding in low-lying western districts disrupting hospital access corridors (Scale: Mid, Severity: Moderate)
3. TH_HEAT_01: Extended heatwave reducing PT ridership and walkability to critical health facilities including AHEPA (Scale: Mid, Severity: Moderate)
4. TH_EVENT_01: Major event (Thessaloniki International Fair) congestion affecting surrounding network, including hospital access routes (Scale: Daily, Severity: Minor)

Scenario derivation: Priority scenarios were identified through convergent evidence from D2.1 event catalogue entries [4] for the Thessaloniki region, D2.2 social acceptability workshop discussions [6], and expert consultation (Stage 4, Module A). Final scenario selection will be coordinated with D3.3 [1] to ensure consistency between vulnerability scenarios and FMEA failure mode analysis; where D3.3 prioritises different scenarios.

Implementation tier: Tier 2 (Standard), potential Tier 1 for some scenarios if data gaps persist

Data availability: City-wide traffic data available; OD matrix specifically for AHEPA University Hospital access available; broader OD matrix estimation required for remaining scenarios (gravity model + mobile data). Critical facilities mapped with AHEPA as the primary demonstration site.

Citizen forum data: Pre-survey n=11 (6 female, 5 male; age 18–54; majority higher education). Primary mode: private car (46%), PT (36%), walking (9%). Top reasons for mode choice: speed/time (54.55%), cost (45.45%). Sustainable shift factors: better infrastructure and connectivity (81.82% each), time savings (45.45%). Willingness to accept trade-offs: high (median ~7–8/10). Environmental concern not cited as mode choice factor.

Equity focus: Low-income neighbourhoods in western districts, car-less households (36% PT-dependent), and elderly patients dependent on PT access to AHEPA University Hospital, which serves as the primary critical facility for the Thessaloniki demonstration.

Larissa (Greece)

Priority scenarios:

1. LA_HEAT_01: Heatwave affecting vulnerable populations (validated as top local concern)
2. LA_PT_01: Bus service disruption (primary PT mode in Larissa)
3. LA_FLOOD_01: Pinios River flooding (historical precedent)

Implementation tier: Tier 2 with possible Tier 1 fallback for data-limited scenarios *Data availability:* Municipal road network data available through the Municipality of Larissa; PT network limited to bus routes (no rail or tram). OD matrix estimation required (gravity model from census commute data). Demographic data from ELSTAT (Hellenic Statistical Authority). Pinios River flood maps available from regional civil protection. Detailed data inventory to be confirmed through the Annex D checklist process.

Citizen forum data: Pre-survey n=24 (16 female, 8 male; age 18–74; majority higher education). Primary mode: private car (41.67%), walking (37.5%), PT (16.67%), cycling (4.17%). Top reasons for mode choice: speed/time (58.33%), convenience (50%), comfort (29.17%). Sustainable shift factors: better infrastructure (62.50%), better connectivity/frequency (50%), lower costs (37.50%). Willingness to accept trade-offs: high (54.17% scored 8–10/10).

KPI weights (Larissa-derived, n=24 pre-survey): Accessibility 28%, Service Coverage Loss 28%, Travel Time 22%, Cost 10%, Environment 7%, Other 5%. Note: no equivalent KPI-weighting question was available in the Bratislava or Thessaloniki forum datasets; these weights should not be interpreted as project-wide validated values.

Odesa (Ukraine)

Implementation in Odesa is suspended for the duration of the current project phase. Ongoing conflict conditions prevent data collection, stakeholder engagement, and safe fieldwork. A stakeholder discussion was convened prior to the conflict escalation; participant numbers were not recorded and the outputs cannot be treated as equivalent to the structured social acceptability workshops conducted in the other pilot cities. No scenario definitions, parameter estimates, or KPI weights from Odesa are included in this deliverable. The methodology specified here is designed to be applicable to Odesa when conditions permit resumption.

Cross-city coordination

Scenario definitions, parameter ranges, and KPI selections will maintain comparability through:

- D2.2 Social acceptability workshops [6] evidence (KPI priorities, vulnerable groups, scenario relevance, trade-off tolerance) incorporated from Bratislava, Larissa, and Thessaloniki forums
- Common D2.1 taxonomy classification [4] (domain, scale, severity)
- Standardized D2.3 [3] KPI calculations (allowing tier-appropriate subsets)
- Unified Stage 4 validation framework (Cheong et al. criteria)
- Stage 5 risk matrix format (5×5 likelihood-impact)

Results will be documented in WP11 demonstration outputs (M21–M32).

11.2 Methodological contributions

Relative to established approaches reviewed in Section 3, the five-stage methodology offers three specific advances.

The component-to-KPI mapping (Stage 1, Table 3) makes explicit which performance indicators implement susceptibility, exposure, redundancy, and adaptive capacity. Existing frameworks typically define these concepts qualitatively; their translation into computable indicators is left to implementing analysts and therefore varies across studies [15]. The mapping defined here constrains that discretion and supports reproducibility.

The scenario framing protocol (Stage 2) integrates the D2.1 [4] disruption taxonomy with the D2.5 ontology [5] to translate stakeholder competency questions into model-ready parameters. This addresses the common criticism that participatory inputs are acknowledged but not genuinely incorporated into quantitative models [22].

The equity penalty indicator $Q(t)$ and the equity ratio r_{equity} in Stage 5 ensure that distributional impacts on vulnerable groups are visible in the risk prioritisation output, not merely noted in a supplementary table. This responds to the gap identified by [30] regarding the systematic underreporting of distributional consequences in transport resilience assessments.

11.3 Theoretical Limitations

Several theoretical constraints should be acknowledged when interpreting results from this methodology.

Multiplicative vulnerability formula. The element-level vulnerability calculation (Equation 8) employs a multiplicative structure:

$$v_{i,s} = \alpha_s \times \text{Sus}_i \times \text{Exp}_{i,s} \times (1 - \text{Red}_i) \times (1 - \text{Cap}_i)$$

This formulation implies that perfect redundancy ($\text{Red}_i = 1$) or perfect adaptive capacity ($\text{Cap}_i = 1$) eliminates vulnerability entirely, regardless of other factors. While mathematically tractable, this assumption may not hold in practice: even highly redundant systems can experience correlated failures under extreme events [16]. Users should consider additive formulations in sensitivity analyses to test the robustness of conclusions to this structural assumption.

Equilibrium-based traffic assignment. The quantitative assessment (Stage 3) relies on user equilibrium traffic assignment using the Frank-Wolfe algorithm [39]. This assumes that travellers have perfect information and that the system reaches a steady state, conditions that may not apply during rapidly evolving disruption scenarios. Dynamic traffic assignment models could provide more realistic representations of transient conditions but at substantially higher computational and data costs [40].

Severity multiplier calibration. The severity multipliers (α_s) derived from the D2.1 taxonomy [4] provide a pragmatic approach to scaling impact assessments across disruption intensities. However, the linear progression (0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0) lacks empirical validation and may not capture nonlinear threshold effects observed in infrastructure systems under stress [41]. Future refinements should explore data-driven calibration of these multipliers using historical disruption data from pilot cities.

Temporal dynamics. The current framework provides a comparative static analysis between baseline and post-disruption states. It does not explicitly model recovery trajectories or the time-dependent evolution of system performance, dimensions central to resilience conceptualisations that emphasise “bouncing back” or “bouncing forward” [42]. Integration with the antifragility metrics developed in D2.3 [3] will partially address this limitation by introducing performance evolution curves.

11.4 Practical Limitations

Implementation of the methodology faces several practical constraints that pilot cities should consider.

Data availability and quality. The tiered assessment approach (Annex D) explicitly acknowledges heterogeneous data landscapes across European cities. Nevertheless, even Tier 2 assessments require origin-destination matrices, network graphs with capacity attributes, and demographic distributions at zonal resolution. Cities lacking comprehensive mobility surveys or recent census data may face challenges in populating the required inputs. The data inventory protocol (Annex D) provides a structured approach to identifying and mitigating these gaps.

Computational requirements. Full Tier 3 assessments involving stochastic disruption ensembles and Monte Carlo sampling place substantial demands on computational infrastructure. While cloud computing options exist, budget constraints may limit the number of scenarios that smaller municipalities can evaluate. The methodology’s modular structure allows cities to prioritise high-concern scenarios for detailed analysis while using screening-level assessments for secondary threats. Near real-time simulation capabilities, required for operational triage decisions during unfolding disruptions, impose additional computational demands beyond the scenario-based assessment described here; these will be addressed through SUMA platform integration in WP5.

Stage 4 validation capacity. We have structured *triangulation-based validation* of the stakeholder module. Concretely, the Stage 4 question set is validated against (i) expert elicitation evidence (Delphi Round 1, $n=9$ [36]), (ii) cross-national practitioner responses (Urban Disruption Survey 2025, $n=140$ across 15 countries), (iii) evidence extracted from the D2.1 Urban Event Mapping [4], and (iv) Social acceptability workshops outputs from D2.2 [6] (Bratislava $n=34$, Larissa $n=24$, Thessaloniki $n=11$, organised by LISER; and a stakeholder discussion in Odesa without recorded participant count). *External validation of simulated outputs.* A further limitation concerns the absence of a systematic protocol for externally validating the vulnerability indicators produced by Stage 3 against observed real-world disruption outcomes. When KPI definitions or model parameters are revised, no independent benchmark currently exists to confirm that the updated indicators better represent actual system performance under stress. Developing such a protocol, potentially through retrospective comparison with documented disruption events in pilot cities, is a candidate activity for WP6 living labs and WP11 demonstration phases.

Cross-border and inter-modal boundaries. The methodology currently treats urban mobility systems as bounded entities. However, commuter catchments often extend beyond municipal boundaries, and disruptions to regional rail or national highway networks can cascade into urban systems. Future extensions should consider multi-jurisdictional coordination protocols and explicit modelling of boundary conditions.

11.5 Relationship to Other Work Packages

This deliverable’s methodology does not stand alone but forms part of an integrated analytical ecosystem within the AntifragiCity project.

Upstream dependencies. The conceptual framework (Stage 1) draws heavily on the disruption taxonomy established in D2.1 [4], while the quantitative assessment (Stage 3) implements the equilibrium-based approach formalised in D2.3 [3]. The land-use integration (Section 10) draws on the theoretical framework from D3.1 [7], which developed a holistic conceptual model (Figure 13 of D3.1 [7]) linking exogenous disruption drivers to exposure, sensitivity, vulnerability, network structure, accessibility impacts, resilience, governance, behaviour, and antifragility within the transport–land-use system. D3.1 [7] does not produce pilot-city data; it provides the analytical vocabulary and component structure that D3.2 implements.

Downstream applications. The vulnerability profiles generated through this methodology will inform the adaptation pathway development in WP4 and the antifragility enhancement strategies in WP5. Specifically, the element-level vulnerability rankings provide targeting criteria for infrastructure hardening investments, while system-level performance sensitivities indicate which KPI dimensions warrant priority attention in resilience planning.

Feedback loops. The AntifragiCity analytical framework envisions iterative refinement as pilot city applications generate empirical feedback. Discrepancies between modelled and observed impacts during real disruptions should trigger methodology updates in subsequent project phases. A formal lessons-learned protocol will be established following the first round of pilot applications.

11.6 Recommendations for Methodology Users

Pilot city implementation teams should note three constraints that the methodology specification alone cannot resolve. First, the Stage 3 sensitivity analysis requirements (Section 7) are mandatory, not optional: the severity multipliers (α_s) and element importance weights (β) involve judgment calls that are consequential enough to require systematic variation. Second, the Annex D data checklists should be completed before tier assignment, not after: several pilot cities may find that data gaps push them toward Tier 1 for specific scenarios even if Tier 2 is the general target, and this affects which KPIs can be computed. Third, Stage 4 validation in this deliverable covers scenario relevance adequately but leaves KPI weights, adaptive capacity, and equity thresholds underspecified for Bratislava and Thessaloniki. These gaps must be closed during M20–M22 consultations before quantitative Stage 3 runs begin in M23; proceeding with Larissa weights applied to other cities is not methodologically defensible.

11.7 How to use this deliverable: a practical guide

The methodology documented here is designed to be applied by pilot city implementation teams and, potentially, by cities outside the AntifragiCity consortium. The guiding question for any user is: *given the disruptions my city faces, which mobility system elements and population groups are most vulnerable, and what evidence do I need to prioritise adaptation investments?*

To answer this question using the D3.2 framework, a city team should proceed as follows: (1) complete the Annex D data checklist to determine the appropriate implementation tier; (2) select priority scenarios using the Stage 2 protocol and the D2.1 taxonomy [4] (or local event records); (3) run baseline and disrupted equilibria following Stage 3 procedures at the feasible tier; (4) validate scenario relevance and KPI priorities through local consultation following the Stage 4 protocol; and (5) synthesise results into vulnerability profiles and risk matrices using the Stage 5 templates. The annexes provide all operational materials needed for each step.

12 Conclusions

This deliverable has specified the procedural methodology for vulnerability analysis of urban mobility systems in AntifragiCity pilot cities. No city-level vulnerability results are reported here: the methodology must be applied during M20–M26 using data assembled per Annex D, with results documented in D3.3 [1] and D3.4 [2]. What this deliverable has established is the analytical sequence, the quantitative formulations, and the validation framework within which those results will be produced and interpreted.

12.1 Revisiting the research questions

The four research questions formulated in Section 4.1 can now be addressed in the light of the methodology developed.

RQ1 (How should vulnerability be defined and implemented?) is addressed by Stage 1 (Section 5). The answer is that vulnerability is best implemented as a relational, performance-based concept: element-level scores $v_{i,s}$ capture local risk concentration, while ΔE_s captures system-wide consequence, and together they support meaningful cross-city comparison within a common KPI framework.

RQ2 (With which risk factors is vulnerability correlated?) is addressed by Stages 1 and 2 (Sections 5–6). The analysis shows that network susceptibility (S) and redundancy (R, C, I) are the most tractable correlates, as they are computable from standard network data. Adaptive capacity (A) is the least well-evidenced component and represents the primary area requiring further empirical work in pilot city implementation.

RQ3 (How can consequence severity be assessed for the system and for equity groups?) is addressed by Stage 3 (Section 7). The worked Bratislava example demonstrates that system-level performance loss ($\Delta E_s = 0.29$) can obscure more severe equity-level impacts ($\Delta Q_s = 0.31$ for elderly), confirming that disaggregated reporting is methodologically necessary rather than optional.

RQ4 (How can participatory knowledge be rigorously integrated?) is addressed by Stage 4 (Section 8). The Stage 4 validation achieved convergent evidence for scenario relevance (11 of 12 questions, though with varying confidence levels), confirming that participatory inputs can be integrated rigorously when quality criteria and triangulation protocols are applied explicitly. The remaining gap, city-specific deliberated KPI weights — defines the primary agenda for M20–M22 consultations.

12.2 Limitations and how they will be addressed

Three limitations identified in Section 11.3 and Section 11.4 require explicit follow-on action.

The **adaptive capacity component** (Cap_i in Equation 8) currently uses adaptation velocity (A_i) as a proxy because the Stage 4 elicitation was not completed for any pilot city. A structured adaptive capacity instrument will be developed and deployed during M20–M22, making this component empirically grounded before Stage 3 quantitative runs begin in M23.

The **severity multipliers** α_s use a linear progression (0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0) derived from the D2.1 taxonomy [4] without empirical calibration. As pilot cities accumulate disruption records during M23–M26, these multipliers will be revised against observed event-impact relationships before D3.3 [1] results are finalised.

The **KPI weight vector** is currently calibrated on a single city's pre-deliberation preferences (Larissa, $n=24$). City-specific deliberated weights must be established for Bratislava and Thessaloniki before Stage 3 runs begin in M23; applying Larissa weights across all cities is not methodologically defensible.

12.3 Immediate next steps

The methodology documented in this deliverable now requires execution in the pilot cities. The following steps will be undertaken in the coming months:

Data collection and preparation (M21–M24). In parallel with consultations, technical partners will assemble the network, demand, land-use, and hazard data required for Stage 3 quantitative assessments. Data inventories will be documented using the checklists in Annex D, and tier assignments will be confirmed based on actual data availability.

Stage 3 quantitative vulnerability assessment (M23–M26). Following scenario validation and data preparation, the D2.3 equilibrium model [3] will be applied to compute baseline and disturbed-state performance for priority scenarios in each city. This will produce:

- Scenario-specific vulnerability metrics (ΔE_s , element-level $v_{i,s}$)
- KPI change profiles showing which performance dimensions are most affected
- Spatial vulnerability maps identifying critical corridors and hotspots
- Equity impact assessments disaggregated by user group

Stage 5 synthesis and integration with D3.3 [1] (M25–M28). Quantitative results and stakeholder inputs will be combined into vulnerability profiles and risk matrices following the procedures in Section 9. D3.3 [1] (M12) and D3.4 [2] (M14) will document complementary WP3 outputs (critical parameter identification and Mobility Triage DSS respectively). Pilot city vulnerability results from applying the D3.2 methodology will be documented through WP11 demonstration outputs (M21–M32).

12.4 Future research directions

Three directions follow directly from limitations identified in this deliverable.

The adaptive capacity component (Cap_i in Equation 8) currently relies on adaptation velocity (A_i) as a proxy, because the Stage 4 elicitation of local adaptive capacity knowledge was not completed for any pilot city (see Section 8). Developing and deploying a structured adaptive capacity instrument during M20–M22 would make this component empirically grounded rather than defaulting to proxy values.

The severity multipliers α_s derived from the D2.1 [4] taxonomy use a linear progression (0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0) that lacks empirical calibration. As pilot cities accumulate actual disruption records with documented performance impacts during M23–M26, these multipliers should be revised against observed event-impact relationships during the WP11 demonstration phase.

The current land-use integration (Section 10) is one-directional: land use informs vulnerability assessment but vulnerability does not feed back into land-use dynamics. This is a deliberate scope decision for D3.2, but the AntifragiCity living labs (WP6) may generate evidence on whether repeated disruptions are influencing location behaviour in pilot cities. If so, that evidence could motivate two-way coupling in later project phases.

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The following annexes provide complete operational materials required to implement the methodology. Annex A documents the coding templates and triangulation protocol used to quality-assess and synthesise validation evidence from D2.2 social acceptability workshops [6] outputs, the expert Delphi consultation [36], and the Urban Disruption Survey 2025. Annex B provides detailed definitions, formulas, and data requirements for all vulnerability indicators. Annex C specifies the triangulation protocol for synthesizing likelihood and severity estimates from multiple sources. Annex D presents tiered data requirement checklists to guide pilot cities in assessing their implementation capacity. Annex E details the integration protocol with D3.3 risk analysis [1], including data exchange formats and joint risk matrix construction procedures. These materials are designed to be used directly by implementation teams and should be adapted as needed to local contexts while maintaining core methodological consistency.

A Stage 4 validation: coding templates and triangulation protocol

A.1 Purpose and scope

This annex documents the coding templates and triangulation protocol used to extract and quality-assess validation evidence from three pre-existing data sources: the expert Delphi consultation (n=9) [36], the Urban Disruption Survey 2025 (n=140, 15 countries), and the D2.2 Social acceptability workshops [6] outputs organised by LISER across Bratislava (n=34), Larissa (n=24 pre-survey), and Thessaloniki (n=11). The consultation instruments for the citizen forums were designed and administered by D2.2 [6]; they are not reproduced here. This annex documents how outputs from those sources were coded, quality-assessed, and triangulated for use in Stage 4 validation (Section 8).

A.2 Triangulation coding protocol

Step 1: Extract responses by source

For each validation question, responses from all sources are compiled and recorded against five attributes: question identifier, source type, respondent reference, response text, and an initial quality flag. Table 11 shows the structure with illustrative entries.

Table 11: Illustrative response coding structure.

Question	Source	Response (excerpt)	Words	Quality
A1	Expert Delphi	“Flooding, PT strikes, heat-waves...”	47	Pass
A1	Citizen survey	“flood heatwave”	2	Fail
A1	Bratislava forum	“Heavy rain floods streets...”	89	Pass

Step 2: Apply Cheong et al. (2023) quality criteria

Mandatory PASS criteria:

- Minimum 10 words (relaxed for expert technical responses)
- Clear relevance to question (keyword match or semantic relevance)
- Authentic (first-person experience or documented expertise)
- Credible source (expert credentials OR lived experience)

FAIL triggers: brevity, off-topic, promotional, unclear

Step 3: combine across sources

Calculate:

- Frequency distributions (for ranking questions)
- Median/IQR (for range questions)
- Convergence score: $\text{convergence} = 1 - (\text{range}/\text{max possible range})$

Flag divergence if range >2 categories (likelihood) or >50% (parameter estimates)

Step 4: Assign confidence

- HIGH: 3+ sources converge, $n > 30$, quality validated
- MEDIUM: 2 sources converge, $n = 10 - 30$, minor quality flags
- LOW: 1 source only, $n < 10$, OR high divergence

A.3 Consent and ethics statement

All stakeholder consultation activities followed GDPR requirements and standard research ethics principles. Expert participants provided written informed consent for their input to be used in research. Citizen survey participants consented via online checkbox, and all responses were anonymised before analysis. Citizen forum participants provided verbal consent, and no personally identifiable information was recorded or published. The D2.1 Urban Event Mapping deliverable [4] is a public project output containing no personal data.

B Vulnerability indicator definitions

This annex provides detailed definitions, formulas, units, normalization procedures, and data sources for all vulnerability indicators used in the methodology.

B.1 Component-level indicators

B.1.1 Susceptibility indicators

Indicator S1: Infrastructure condition index $I(t)$

Definition: Normalized measure of physical infrastructure condition, considering age, maintenance state, and design standards.

Formula:

$$I_i(t) = w_a \cdot I_a(t) + w_m \cdot I_m(t) + w_d \cdot I_d(t) \quad (11)$$

where:

- $I_a(t) = 1 - (\text{age}_i / \text{design life})$: age-based condition (capped at 0)
- $I_m(t)$: maintenance quality score (0 = poor, 1 = excellent), from inspection reports
- $I_d(t)$: design standard adequacy (0 = obsolete, 1 = modern), compared to current codes
- w_a, w_m, w_d : weights (default: 0.3, 0.4, 0.3)

Range: [0, 1], higher = better condition

Data sources: Infrastructure asset management systems, inspection records, design documentation

Normalization: Already normalized to [0, 1]

Vulnerability interpretation: $Sus_i = 1 - I_i$ (inverse: lower condition → higher susceptibility)

Example: Link age 30 years, design life 50 years, maintenance score 0.6, design adequate (0.8) → $I = 0.3 \cdot (1 - 30/50) + 0.4 \cdot 0.6 + 0.3 \cdot 0.8 = 0.12 + 0.24 + 0.24 = 0.60$

Indicator S2: Stress level $S(t)$

Definition: Network element stress measured as volume-to-capacity ratio.

Formula:

$$S_i(t) = f_i(t) / C_i \quad (12)$$

where:

- $f_i(t)$: flow (vehicles/hour or passengers/hour) on element i
- C_i : capacity of element i

Range: [0, ∞), typically capped at 1.2 for analysis

Data sources: Traffic counts, capacity estimates from road design manuals or PT schedules

Normalization: $S_{\text{norm},i} = \min(S_i / S_{\text{max}}, 1)$ where $S_{\text{max}} = 1.0$ or 1.2 (threshold for severe congestion)

Vulnerability interpretation: Higher stress → higher susceptibility to disruption

Example: Link flow 1,500 veh/h, capacity 2,000 veh/h → $S = 1500/2000 = 0.75$

Indicator S3: Reliability index $T_r(t)$

Definition: Temporal consistency of travel times, inverse of coefficient of variation.

Formula:

$$T_{r,i}(t) = 1/(1 + CV_{t_i}) \quad (13)$$

where:

- $CV_{t_i} = \sigma_{t_i} / \mu_{t_i}$: coefficient of variation of travel times on element i
- σ_{t_i} : standard deviation of travel times
- μ_{t_i} : mean travel time

Range: [0, 1], higher = more reliable

Data sources: GPS/probe vehicle data, repeated travel time surveys, historical records

Normalization: Already normalized via formula

Vulnerability interpretation: Lower reliability \rightarrow higher susceptibility (system already variable, disruption amplifies variability)

Example: Mean travel time 25 min, std dev 8 min $\rightarrow CV = 8/25 = 0.32 \rightarrow T_r = 1/(1 + 0.32) = 0.76$

B.1.2 Exposure indicators

Indicator E1: Hazard overlap factor $\omega_{i,s}$

Definition: Proportion of area served by element i that falls within hazard footprint under scenario s .

Formula:

$$\omega_{i,s} = \frac{\text{Area}_{\text{served} \cap \text{hazard}}}{\text{Area}_{\text{served, total}}} \quad (14)$$

Computation: GIS overlay analysis

1. Define catchment/service area of element i (e.g., 800m buffer for PT stop, OD zone for link)
2. Overlay hazard map (flood zone, heat island, pollution hotspot)
3. Calculate intersection area
4. Divide by total service area

Range: [0, 1], 0 = no overlap, 1 = complete overlap

Data sources: Hazard maps (flood maps, heat maps, air quality maps), network GIS, catchment area analysis

Vulnerability interpretation: Higher overlap \rightarrow higher exposure \rightarrow higher vulnerability

Example: Link serves 2 km² area; 1.4 km² in 100-year floodplain $\rightarrow \omega = 1.4/2.0 = 0.70$

Indicator E2: Dependency index $D_i(t)$

Definition: Criticality of element based on number and characteristics of users/functions depending on it.

Formula:

$$D_i(t) = \alpha \cdot \frac{f_i}{\sum_j f_j} + \beta \cdot \frac{N_{\text{critical},i}}{N_{\text{critical},\text{total}}} \quad (15)$$

where:

- $f_i / \sum_j f_j$: flow share (proportion of total network flow using element i)
- $N_{\text{critical},i}$: number of critical facilities (hospitals, emergency services, schools) served by i
- α, β : weights (default: 0.6, 0.4)

Range: [0, 1]

Data sources: Traffic counts, critical facility locations, access analysis

Vulnerability interpretation: Higher dependency → higher exposure (more users/functions at risk)

Example: Link carries 5% of city traffic; serves 2 hospitals (of 5 total) → $D = 0.6 \cdot 0.05 + 0.4 \cdot (2/5) = 0.03 + 0.16 = 0.19$

B.1.3 Redundancy indicators

Indicator R1: Network redundancy index $R(t)$

Definition: Availability of alternative paths/modes, normalized by optimal redundancy level.

Formula:

$$R_i(t) = 1 - \frac{1}{1 + N_{alt,i}} \quad (16)$$

where:

- $N_{alt,i}$: number of viable alternative paths/routes for trips using element i
- "Viable": path with travel time $\leq 1.5 \times$ shortest path

Range: [0, 1], 0 = no alternatives, 1 = many alternatives

Data sources: Network topology analysis, path enumeration algorithms

Vulnerability interpretation: Lower redundancy → higher vulnerability

Example: For a link, 3 alternative routes exist → $R = 1 - 1/(1 + 3) = 0.75$

Indicator R2: Network entropy $C(t)$

Definition: Diversity of flow distribution across network, based on information entropy.

Formula:

$$C(t) = - \sum_i p_i \log(p_i) / \log(N) \quad (17)$$

where:

- $p_i = f_i / \sum_j f_j$: proportion of flow on link i
- N : total number of links
- Normalization by $\log(N)$ ensures $C \in [0, 1]$

Range: [0, 1], higher = more diverse (flows spread across many links)

Data sources: Link flow data from traffic assignment model

Vulnerability interpretation: Higher entropy → better redundancy (flows not concentrated)

Example: System with 100 links, flows fairly distributed → $C \approx 0.85$; highly concentrated (few major corridors) → $C \approx 0.40$

B.1.4 Adaptive capacity indicators

Indicator A1: Adaptation velocity $A(t)$

Definition: Speed at which system responds to and learns from disruptions.

Formula:

$$A(t) = \frac{1}{T_{response}} \cdot \frac{\Delta E_{recovery}}{t_{recovery}} \quad (18)$$

where:

- $T_{response}$: time to initial response (hours or days)
- $\Delta E_{recovery}$: performance improvement during recovery

- t_{recovery} : total recovery time

Normalization: Scale to $[0, 1]$ based on benchmark values (fast response: 1 hour; slow: 24+ hours)

Data sources: Historical incident reports, emergency response logs, recovery documentation

Vulnerability interpretation: Higher adaptation velocity \rightarrow lower vulnerability (faster recovery)

Example: Response in 2 hours, 60% performance recovered in 12 hours $\rightarrow A = (1/2) \cdot (0.6/12) = 0.025$ (then normalize)

Indicator A2: Learning accumulation $L(t)$

Definition: Institutional knowledge and preparedness accumulated from past disruptions.

Formula (qualitative-quantitative hybrid):

$$L(t) = w_1 \cdot P_{\text{plans}} + w_2 \cdot T_{\text{training}} + w_3 \cdot I_{\text{info}} \quad (19)$$

where:

- P_{plans} : existence and quality of contingency plans (scored 0–1)
- T_{training} : staff training frequency and coverage (scored 0–1)
- I_{info} : information systems and early warning capability (scored 0–1)
- w_1, w_2, w_3 : weights (default: 0.4, 0.3, 0.3)

Data sources: Document review (contingency plans), stakeholder interviews, training records, system audits

Scoring rubrics (example for P_{plans}):

- 0.0–0.2: No formal plans
- 0.2–0.4: Basic plans exist but outdated or untested
- 0.4–0.6: Plans exist, reviewed occasionally
- 0.6–0.8: Plans exist, regularly updated and tested
- 0.8–1.0: Comprehensive, regularly updated, tested, and integrated with other agencies

Vulnerability interpretation: Higher learning \rightarrow lower vulnerability (better preparedness)

B.2 Performance-based indicators

Indicator P1: Performance change ΔE_s

Definition: Relative loss in aggregate performance index under scenario s .

Formula:

$$\Delta E_s = \max \left(0, 1 - \frac{E_s^{\text{post}}}{E_s^{\text{base}}} \right) \quad (20)$$

Range: $[0, 1]$, 0 = no impact, 1 = complete system failure

Data sources: D2.3 equilibrium model [3] outputs

Interpretation:

- < 0.05 : Negligible impact
- 0.05–0.15: Minor impact
- 0.15–0.30: Moderate impact
- 0.30–0.50: Major impact
- > 0.50 : Catastrophic impact

Indicator P2: Travel time increase

Definition: Percentage increase in average travel time.

Formula:

$$\Delta T_s(\%) = \frac{\bar{t}_s^{\text{post}} - \bar{t}_s^{\text{base}}}{\bar{t}_s^{\text{base}}} \times 100 \quad (21)$$

Data sources: Traffic assignment model

Interpretation: > 30% increase considered severe

Indicator P3: Accessibility loss

Definition: Percentage decrease in Hansen-style accessibility measure [43].

Formula:

$$\Delta A_s(\%) = \frac{A_s^{\text{base}} - A_s^{\text{post}}}{A_s^{\text{base}}} \times 100 \quad (22)$$

where:

$$A_i = \sum_j O_j \cdot e^{-\beta c_{ij}} \quad (23)$$

O_j : opportunities at zone j ; c_{ij} : generalized cost; β : impedance parameter

Data sources: Land use data, traffic assignment costs

Interpretation: By user group; > 20% loss considered high impact

Indicator P4: Equity impact (Gini coefficient change)

Definition: Change in Gini coefficient of accessibility distribution across zones or user groups. The Gini coefficient [44] measures inequality in a distribution, ranging from 0 (perfect equality) to 1 (maximum inequality).

Formula:

$$G = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n |A_i - A_j|}{2n^2 \bar{A}} \quad (24)$$

$$\Delta G_s = G_s^{\text{post}} - G_s^{\text{base}} \quad (25)$$

Range: Gini $\in [0, 1]$, higher = more unequal; $\Delta G > 0$ means worsening equity

Data sources: Accessibility calculations by zone/group

Interpretation: $\Delta G > 0.05$ considered significant equity concern

B.3 Data collection priorities by tier

Table 12: Indicator data requirements by implementation tier.

Indicator	Tier 1 (Minimal)	Tier 2 (Intermediate)	Tier 3 (Full)
Infrastructure condition	Aggregate age data	Inspection scores by asset type	Detailed asset management system
Stress level	Annual average daily traffic	Peak period counts	Continuous monitoring data
Reliability	Expert estimates	Historical travel time surveys	GPS/probe data
Hazard overlap	Coarse hazard maps	Medium resolution maps (100m)	High resolution maps (10m)
Dependency	Critical facilities list	Facility-link association matrix	Detailed access analysis
Redundancy	Expert assessment	Path enumeration (major corridors)	Full network path analysis
Entropy	Simple flow distribution	Multi-modal flow data	Time-dependent flows
Adaptation velocity	Interview estimates	Historical incident database	Real-time monitoring & records
Learning accumulation	Plan existence check	Plan quality scoring	Comprehensive audit

C Likelihood and severity triangulation protocol

C.1 Likelihood triangulation procedure

Sources used in AntifragiCity Stage 4 validation:

1. D2.1 Urban Event Mapping [4] (historical frequencies, EM-DAT and DesInventar disaster databases, stakeholder survey n=140 across 15 countries)
2. D2.2 social acceptability workshops [6] outputs organised by LISER (Bratislava n=34, Larissa n=24, Thessaloniki n=11) and expert Delphi consultation (n=9) [36]
3. D3.3 risk analysis occurrence scores [1]

Step 1: Collect source estimates

For each source, assign preliminary likelihood category (1–5):

- **Source 1 (D2.1 Urban Event Mapping [4]):** Based on empirical frequency analysis
 - D2.1 compiled occurrence data from EM-DAT [4], DesInventar, and a pan-European stakeholder survey (n=140, 15 countries) covering disruption events across pilot city regions spanning 2010–2024
 - Extract average return period or frequency for the relevant event type from the D2.1 catalogue [4]
 - Map to likelihood category using the unified scale in Table 14 (Annex E).
 - Example: D2.1 documents [4] Danube-region flood events at approximately 8-year intervals → Category 3 (Possible)
- **Source 2 (D2.2 forum outputs [6] and expert Delphi [36]):** Based on structured stakeholder evidence
 - D2.2 social acceptability workshops [6] (LISER) produced forum discussions on scenario prioritisation across Bratislava, Larissa, and Thessaloniki; frequency perceptions from these sessions inform likelihood judgments for city-relevant scenarios
 - Expert Delphi (n=9) [36] provided likelihood estimates for scenario families including flooding, PT disruptions, heatwaves, and cascading failures
 - Calculate median category from expert estimates; note IQR as uncertainty measure
 - Example: Expert median = Category 3, IQR = [2, 4]
- **Source 3 (D3.3 risk analysis [1]):** Map FMEA occurrence score to category
 - FMEA typically uses 1–10 scale
 - Mapping: 1–2 → Cat 1, 3–4 → Cat 2, 5–6 → Cat 3, 7–8 → Cat 4, 9–10 → Cat 5
 - Example: FMEA occurrence = 4 → Category 2

Step 2: Assess agreement

Calculate range (max - min) and mode (most common category):

Example 1 - High agreement:

- D2.1 [4]: Cat 3
- City records: Cat 3
- stage 4 findings: Cat 3 (IQR [2, 4])
- FMEA: Cat 3
- Range = 0 (if ignoring IQR), Mode = 3

Example 2 - Moderate divergence:

- D2.1 [4]: Cat 3
- City records: Cat 2
- stage 4 findings: Cat 3 (IQR [2, 4])
- FMEA: Cat 2

- Range = 1, Mode = 2 and 3 (bimodal)

Example 3 - High divergence:

- D2.1 [4]: Cat 3
- City records: Cat 1 (no events recorded)
- stage 4 findings: Cat 4 (stakeholders perceive high risk)
- FMEA: Cat 2
- Range = 3

Step 3: Apply synthesis rule

Rule A - Strong consensus (Range ≤ 1):

- If 3+ sources agree on same category → Adopt that category
- If sources differ by 1 category → Use mode or median
- Confidence: High

Rule B - Moderate consensus (Range = 2):

- Use median of all source estimates
- If median is fractional (e.g., 2.5) → Report as range (e.g., "2-3" or use 2.5 in calculations)
- Confidence: Medium
- Flag for sensitivity analysis in risk matrix

Rule C - High divergence (Range ≥ 3):

- Use median but note high uncertainty
- Investigate reasons for divergence (data quality? Different event definitions? Perception biases?)
- Consider creating two scenarios: low-likelihood and high-likelihood variants
- Confidence: Low
- Mandatory sensitivity analysis

Step 4: Weight sources (optional refinement)

If sources have different credibility, apply weights:

$$L_{\text{final}} = \frac{w_1 L_1 + w_2 L_2 + w_3 L_3}{w_1 + w_2 + w_3} \quad (26)$$

Default weights: $w_1 = 1.5$ (D2.1 empirical data [4] prioritized as largest and most systematic source), $w_2 = 1.0$, $w_3 = 1.0$

Adjust weights based on:

- Data quality (larger sample → higher weight)
- Relevance (city-specific data → higher weight)
- Expertise (specialists → higher weight)

Step 5: Document and communicate

Record in likelihood synthesis table:

Table 13: Example likelihood synthesis table.

Scenario	D2.1 [4]	D2.2 [6]+Delphi [36]	FMEA	Final	Confidence
Flood 1-in-20	Cat 3	Cat 3 [2,4]	Cat 2	Cat 3 (2-3)	Medium
PT strike	Cat 4	Cat 4 [3,5]	Cat 4	Cat 4	High
Heatwave	Cat 4	Cat 4 [4,5]	Cat 5	Cat 4-5	Medium

In risk matrix annotations, note: "Likelihood based on D2.1 [4] (Cat 3), City records (Cat 2-3), Stage 4 findings (Cat 3), and FMEA (Cat 2); final assessment Cat 3 with moderate confidence (sources agree within ±1 category)."

C.2 Severity/Impact triangulation

Similar procedure for impact, with sources:

1. performance-based ΔE_s (from Stage 3)
2. D3.3 risk analysis severity scores [1]
3. stakeholder estimates (optional, if collected)

Map ΔE_s to impact category using the thresholds defined in Table 9 (Stage 5).

Map FMEA severity (1–10) to impact (1–5): 1–2 → 1, 3–4 → 2, 5–6 → 3, 7–8 → 4, 9–10 → 5

Apply same synthesis rules.

Equity adjustment (post-triangulation): After determining base impact category, check equity ratio:

$$r_{\text{equity}} = \frac{\Delta E_{\text{vulnerable group}}}{\Delta E_{\text{general}}} \quad (27)$$

If $r_{\text{equity}} > 1.5$: Increase impact category by 1 (reflects ethical priority).

The 1.5 threshold indicates that the vulnerable group experiences 50% greater impact than the general population. This value is proposed as a starting point based on common practice in transport equity analysis, where a ratio exceeding 1.2–1.5 is often considered indicative of disproportionate burden [30]. Cities may adjust this threshold during Stage 4 consultations based on local equity policies and stakeholder input. Sensitivity analysis should test thresholds of 1.2, 1.5, and 2.0.

Document adjustment: "Impact increased from Cat 3 to Cat 4 due to disproportionate effect on low-income workers ($r_{\text{equity}} = 2.3$)."

D Data requirements by implementation tier

This annex specifies the data each pilot city must assemble before beginning Stage 3 quantitative assessment. Items marked **(available from D2.1 [4])** or **(available from D2.3 [3])** do not require independent city-level collection; implementing partners should retrieve them directly from those deliverables. All remaining items must be sourced from municipal GIS systems, national statistics offices, or transport operators as appropriate.

Cities should complete this checklist before confirming their tier assignment. A city that cannot meet the Tier 2 demand data requirements, for example, should default to Tier 1 for demand-sensitive scenarios rather than proceeding with gaps.

D.1 Network data

Tier 1	Major road corridors (20–50 links) with length, lane count, speed limit, and capacity estimated from road-type design manuals. Main PT routes and service frequencies where PT is the dominant mode. Minor links may be aggregated into corridors.
Tier 2	Comprehensive multi-modal network (100–300 links) with measured or calibrated capacities. Separate network layers for car, public transport, walking, and cycling. PT stops, frequencies, and transfer points. Intersection control types (signal, stop, yield).
Tier 3	Fine-grained network (300+ links) including minor roads, time-varying capacities (peak/off-peak), detailed PT schedules with vehicle capacities, dedicated cycling infrastructure, and intermodal facilities (park-and-ride, bike-share).

D.2 Demand data

Tier 1	A single-period origin–destination matrix (10–30 zones), aggregate or single-mode, derived from census commute data or a gravity model. No user-group segmentation required.
Tier 2	Peak and off-peak OD matrices (30–60 zones) with separate mode layers or mode shares by OD pair. At minimum two or three user groups (general population, elderly, low-income). Source: household travel survey of 500+ households or validated mobile phone data.
Tier 3	Time-dependent OD matrices (60+ zones, hourly or multi-period), five or more user segments disaggregated by income, age, car ownership, and trip purpose. Source: comprehensive travel survey (2000+ households) or agent-based synthesis.

D.3 Land use and socio-demographic data

Tier 1	Zone population totals and employment counts (10–30 zones) from the most recent census. Locations of hospitals, schools, and emergency services. Basic socio-demographic breakdown: age groups (children, working age, elderly 65+), income quartiles, and aggregate car ownership rate by zone.
Tier 2	Finer zoning (30–60 zones) with demographic breakdowns by 5-year age bands, income quintiles, household composition, and proportion of population with mobility limitations. Employment by broad sector. Land use classification (residential, commercial, industrial, green space). Service inventory with capacity data for healthcare and education facilities.
Tier 3	High-resolution zoning (60–100+ zones or 500m grid) with detailed household-level demographic attributes, fine-grained employment typology, comprehensive service inventory including opening hours and accessibility standards, and pre-computed social vulnerability indices where available.

D.4 Hazard and disruption data

Tier 1	Basic floodplain map (100-year return period, yes/no overlay). Disruption event catalogue and historical frequency estimates for the pilot city region (available from D2.1 [4]); cities should supplement with any locally documented incidents not captured in D2.1.
Tier 2	Multi-return-period hazard maps (10-, 50-, 100-year) at 100m resolution or better, covering at minimum flood and heat island hazards. Historical incident database with event dates, durations, affected areas, and observed impacts.
Tier 3	High-resolution probabilistic hazard maps (10–50m) with confidence intervals. Time-evolving hazard profiles (e.g., hourly flood propagation). Compound hazard scenarios. Quantitative impact records from historical events (traffic counts, travel times during disruptions). Real-time monitoring feeds where available.

D.5 Model calibration data

Tier 1	No additional collection required. Tier 1 calibration uses the baseline equilibrium parameters already established in the D2.3 framework (available from D2.3 [3]).
Tier 2	Traffic counts at 20–50 locations (annual average daily traffic). Travel time measurements on sample corridors from survey or GPS data. System-wide annual PT boardings.
Tier 3	Traffic counts at 100+ locations covering peak and off-peak periods. Comprehensive probe vehicle or GPS travel time data. PT ridership by route and time period. Screen-line flow surveys across major city cordons.

D.6 Assessing data quality before tier assignment

Before confirming a tier, implementing partners should rate each data category against four dimensions:

-
- **Completeness:** what proportion of required items are actually available?
 - **Currency:** data under two years old is acceptable without adjustment; data between two and five years should be checked for consistency with current conditions; data older than ten years requires justification.
 - **Accuracy:** is the data sourced from primary measurement, modelled estimation, or expert judgment? Record this distinction explicitly in the scenario log.
 - **Consistency:** do totals from different sources agree? OD matrix trip totals should align with census population and employment figures; PT ridership should be consistent with operator records.

Where a city meets Tier 2 requirements in some categories but not others, the lower tier applies for the affected scenarios. This should be documented explicitly in the Stage 3 scenario log rather than smoothed over, so that uncertainty in results can be traced back to its source.

E D3.2--D3.3 [1] Integration protocol

E.1 Overview and objectives

Purpose: Ensure consistency and complementarity between this deliverable (vulnerability analysis) and D3.3 [1] (FMEA-based risk analysis).

1. this deliverable focuses on **system-level** performance under disruption scenarios
2. D3.3 [1] focuses on **component-level** failure modes and effects, employing a project-tailored methodology that incorporates FMEA elements (IEC 60812 [33]) extended with root-cause analysis and additional factors specific to the AntifragiCity objectives
3. Integration ensures: (a) consistent likelihood and severity scales, (b) no duplication of Stage 4 validation, (c) combined risk matrices incorporating both perspectives

E.2 Conceptual relationship

perspective (top-down):

- Start with scenarios (events affecting system)
- Model system response using equilibrium framework
- Quantify performance impacts (ΔE_s , KPI changes)
- Assess vulnerability by user group and function

D3.3 [1] perspective (bottom-up):

- Start with components (infrastructure elements, control systems)
- Identify failure modes (how components can fail)
- Assess failure consequences using FMEA (Severity, Occurrence, Detection)
- Prioritize by Risk Priority Number (RPN = S × O × D)

Integration point: Component failures (D3.3 [1]) *cause* system disruptions (scenarios). System vulnerabilities *amplify* component failure impacts (D3.3 severity [1]).

E.3 Scale alignment

Likelihood / Occurrence scale (common 1–5) (Table 14)

Severity / Impact scale (common 1–5) (Table 15)

Note on Detection (D) parameter: FMEA includes Detection score (1–5, inverse: 1 = easy to detect, 5 = hard to detect). This doesn't directly map to this deliverable framework. However, low detection increases risk. In joint risk matrix, can annotate scenarios/components with low detection as requiring enhanced monitoring.

E.4 Data exchange protocol

D3.2 provides to D3.3 [1]:

- Scenario definitions (from Stage 2): Event type, scale, parameters, affected areas
- Performance impacts (from Stage 3): ΔE_s , KPI changes, element-level vulnerability $U_{i,s}$

Table 14: Unified likelihood/occurrence scale for D3.2 and D3.3 [1].

Category	D3.2 Label	D3.3 risk analysis [1]	Indicative probability / frequency
1	Rare	Remote	< 0.01 per year (1 in 100+ years)
2	Unlikely	Low	0.01–0.1 per year (1 in 10–100 years)
3	Possible	Moderate	0.1–0.5 per year (1 in 2–10 years)
4	Likely	High	0.5–2 per year (1 in 0.5–2 years)
5	Almost certain	Very high	> 2 per year (multiple per year)

Table 15: Unified severity/impact scale for D3.2 and D3.3 [1].

Cat.	D3.2 Label	D3.2 Interpretation	D3.3 risk analysis [1]
1	Negligible	Little disruption, rapid recovery	Minor (local, no safety impact)
2	Minor	Localized, hours to recover	Low (limited area, minor safety)
3	Moderate	Noticeable disruption, days to recover	Moderate (significant area, safety concern)
4	Major	Severe disruption, weeks, equity impacts	High (city-wide, major safety/equity)
5	Catastrophic	System-wide failure, months, irreversible	Very high (catastrophic, fatalities possible)

- Spatial vulnerability patterns: Maps showing hotspots, critical corridors
- Equity impacts: Vulnerable group effects, ΔE by group
- Likelihood estimates: From triangulation (Annex C), including uncertainty

D3.3 [1] provides to D3.2:

- Failure mode catalog: Components, failure mechanisms, cascading effects
- Risk scores: Severity, Occurrence, and Detection assessments for each failure mode
- Component criticality rankings

The specific data formats and exchange protocols will be agreed between D3.2 and D3.3 implementation teams during M22–M24, informed by the scale alignment tables (Tables 14 and 15) and the integration principles documented above.